

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 883075.

METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D3.7

Human rights impact assessment (final version)

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Status-Version:	Final version (v2.0)
Date:	27/03/2023
Distribution level (CO, PU):	PU

Project Number:	GA 883075
Project Title:	METICOS

Title of Deliverable:	Human rights impact assessment (final version)
Due Date of Delivery to the EC:	28/02/2023

Work package responsible for the Deliverable:	WP3 - Evidence transfer to policies on border & external security
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Recommended/mandatory readers:	All partners

Abstract:	Final version of report on human rights impact assessment.
Keyword List:	Human rights impact assessment, HRIA, non-discrimination, privacy, data protection
Disclaimer	This deliverable reflects only the author's views and views and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

Document Description

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.1	20/02/2023	First draft version	VUB
v.0.2	24/02/2023	Table on biases completed by technical partners.	ALL
v.0.3	9/03/2023	Draft version for review	VUB
v0.4	20/03/2023	Comments and suggestions received by AIT and JOAFG	AIT, JOAFG
v1.0	22/03/2023	Integration of comments and suggestion	VUB
v1.1	24/03/2023	Revised draft	VUB
v1.2	27/03/2023	Review	EUC
v2.0	27/03/2023	Final revised	EUC

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures.....	5
List of Tables.....	6
Terms and abbreviations.....	7
Executive Summary	8
1 Introduction.....	9
1.1 General description of METICOS	9
1.2 Document objective and scope	10
1.3 Methodological approach	13
1.3.1 Aim of the human rights impact assessment.....	13
1.3.2 Methodology	14
1.4 Relations with other deliverables.....	17
1.5 Document structure	18
2 Scope of the HRIA.....	20
2.1 Scope 1: Identification of border control technologies being monitored by METICOS.....	20
2.2 Scope 2: Description of the METICOS system	29
3 Identification of impacted groups of persons and impacted Human rights	34
3.1 Identification of the impacted groups of persons.....	34
3.1.1 Identification of groups of persons being impacted by border control technologies ..	34
3.1.1.1 Categories of travellers in the Schengen Border Code	34
3.1.1.2 Categories of travellers based on gender, socio-cultural factors and others	39
3.1.1.3 Border control staff	40
3.1.2 Identification of groups of persons being impacted by the METICOS platform	41
3.2 Identification of impacted Human rights	47
3.2.1 Human Rights that may be impacted by the border technologies	47
3.2.2 Human Rights that may be impacted by the METICOS platform.....	50
4 Evaluation of the impacts on human rights	55
4.1 Evaluation of impacts on human rights deriving from border control technologies.....	55
4.1.1 Impact of the processing of biometric data in travel documents.....	55
4.1.1.1 Description of the types of biometrics included in travel documents.....	55
4.1.1.2 Main privacy risks of fingerprints.....	57

4.1.1.3	Main privacy risks of facial image.....	58
4.1.1.4	Dealing with the impact of biometrics in travel documents within METICOS	59
4.1.2	Impact of the use of large-scale IT systems	61
4.1.2.1	Description of the EU large-scale IT systems	61
4.1.2.2	Impacts of large-scale IT systems on human rights.....	64
4.1.2.3	Dealing with the impact of the use of large-scale IT systems within METICOS	66
4.2	Evaluation of impacts on human rights deriving from the METICOS platform.....	67
4.2.1	Impact of Facial Emotion Recognition.....	68
4.2.1.1	Risks of using facial emotion recognition.....	68
4.2.1.2	Dealing with the impact of Facial Emotion Recognition within METICOS	70
4.2.2	Impact of collecting data from official border control databases and travel documents 70	
4.2.3	Management of AI biases.....	72
5	Mitigation measures.....	120
6	Audit and review of the HRIA.....	124
6.1	Review process of the HRIA.....	124
6.2	Audit process of the HRIA	125
7	Conclusion	126
	Annex 1: Minutes of the workshop on the implications of Artificial Intelligence.....	127
	Annex 2: Minutes of the workshop on travellers' categories and biases	133

List of Figures

FIGURE 1- METHODOLOGY OF METICOS' HRIA	15
FIGURE 2 - DATA FLOW DIAGRAM ENRICHED WITH SECURITY FEATURES.....	33
FIGURE 3 - MAIN PURPOSES OF THE SIX IT LARGE-SCALE SYSTEMS	63
FIGURE 4 - HRIA'S TIMELINE	124

List of Tables

<i>TABLE 1 - HUMAN RIGHT IMPLICATIONS DERIVING FROM METICOS OBJECTIVES AND TOOLS/METHODS</i>	<i>12</i>
<i>TABLE 2 - CONCRETE STEPS OF EACH OF THE STAGES OF THE HRIA</i>	<i>16</i>
<i>TABLE 3 - NO-GATE SOLUTIONS CURRENTLY USED IN EU MEMBER STATES</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>TABLE 4 - TECHNOLOGIES ENVISAGED TO BE MONITORED DURING THE PILOTS</i>	<i>25</i>
<i>TABLE 5 -LIFECYCLE OF DATA WITHIN THE METICOS PLATFORM</i>	<i>29</i>
<i>TABLE 6 - BORDER CHECKS WHICH MAY BE CARRIED OUT AT THE EXTERNAL BORDERS</i>	<i>35</i>
<i>TABLE 7 - SUB-CATEGORIES OF IMPACTED TRAVELLERS</i>	<i>37</i>
<i>TABLE 8 - FACTORS POTENTIALLY IMPACTING HUMAN RIGHTS OF TRAVELLERS</i>	<i>39</i>
<i>TABLE 9 - TARGET GROUPS IMPACTED BY EACH COMPONENT OF THE METICOS PLATFORM</i>	<i>42</i>
<i>TABLE 10 - HORIZON SCANNING OF HUMAN RIGHTS IMPACTED BY BORDER CONTROL TECHNOLOGIES</i>	<i>47</i>
<i>TABLE 11 - IDENTIFIED HUMAN RIGHT IMPACTS OF THE METICOS PLATFORM</i>	<i>52</i>
<i>TABLE 12 - TYPES OF BIOMETRICS INCLUDED IN EDOCUMENTS AND EXEMPTIONS</i>	<i>55</i>
<i>TABLE 13 - TYPE OF BIOMETRICS INCLUDED IN EACH LARGE-SCALE IT SYSTEM</i>	<i>61</i>
<i>TABLE 14 - IDENTIFICATION AND MITIGATION OF BIASES</i>	<i>75</i>
<i>TABLE 15 - SUMMARY OF THE IDENTIFIED MITIGATION MEASURES</i>	<i>120</i>

Terms and abbreviations

ABC	Automated Border Control
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BMS	Border Management System
CFR	EU Charter of Fundamental Rights
DOA	Description of Action
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
EC	European Commission
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Board
EES	Entry/exit system
ENISA	European Union Agency for Network and Information Security
ETIAS	European Travel Information and Authorisation System
FER	Facial Emotion Recognition
FRA	Fundamental Rights Agency
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HRIA	Human Rights Impact Assessment
RFID	Radio frequency identification
RTP	Registered traveller program
SBC	Schengen Borders Code
SIS	Schengen Information System
TCN	Third country nationals
EEA	European economic area
EU	European Union
VIS	Visa Information System

Executive Summary

This document is Deliverable D3.7 “Human rights impact assessment (final version)” of the METICOS project.

In the context of WP3, this Deliverable seeks to identify, evaluate and address the adverse effects on human rights emerging from the METICOS project, and in turn, prevent the METICOS components from breaching fundamental rights and/or negatively impacting socio-cultural factors.

In order to achieve its aim, this Deliverable:

- identifies the scope of the Human Rights Impact Assessment (HRIA);
- identifies the impacted groups of persons and lists the possibly impacted human rights;
- evaluates the impacts of the METICOS platform on human rights;
- formulates mitigation measures;
- provides for an audit and review stage of the HRIA.

The assessment process began at the inception of the project (M03) and will carry on throughout its lifetime (M36). During its process, it analyses all stages of the development process of METICOS to gain an understanding of how each component has approached human rights intersectionality from every aspect of its development.

It is important to note that, in line with the DoA, this Deliverable (D3.7) consists into a “final version of the report on human rights impact assessment”. A first version of the Human rights impact assessment was submitted on M12. In comparison with the first version, this final version addresses issues related to identification and mitigation of biases. It also takes into account the outcomes of two workshops organized in February 2023: the first workshop involved stakeholders from the sector of law and AI to discuss the implications of Artificial Intelligence on fundamental rights; the second one involved stakeholders representing travellers’ categories in order to discuss issues of representativeness during the project’s data collections. Furthermore, it should be noted that this Deliverable was reviewed by the project’s Ethical Advisory Board before submission to the EC.

1 Introduction

1.1 General description of METICOS

The efficient processing of an ever-increasing number of travellers at EU borders calls for more flexible, automated and scalable “no-gate” border security solutions. A “No-Gate Border Crossing Point Solution” is understood to be “a method which enables travellers to cross borders without being slowed down by physical checks, based on automated risk-assessment and/or biometric verification processes”¹. Recent regulatory efforts made by the EU in the context of the “Smart Borders initiative” are meant to frame no-gate border solutions. With this regard, during METICOS’ life cycle (2020-2023), a number of key transformations are planned to take place. Among these, two new systems are expected to have a big impact on the border crossing experience: the Entry/Exit System (EES)² – which is being prepared, however the exact date is still to be determined on EU level – and the European Travel Information and Authorization System (ETIAS)³, which is currently scheduled to be in operation by November 2023.

Concretely, “no gate solutions” – which play an important role in the automation of the clearance process of travellers during security border control – include, amongst others, “airport mobile apps, self-service kiosk check-ins, smart boarding gates, and self-service baggage drop, tagging and tracking, along with biometric technologies”⁴. According to the European Commission, “one main challenge is to manage the flow of travellers and goods arriving at our external borders, while at the same time tackling irregular migration and enhancing our internal security. Any novel technology or organisational measure will need to be accepted by the European citizens”⁵.

In this context, METICOS aims to introduce tools and methods being used in the field of Big Data Analysis in the context of border management in order to evaluate the user’s acceptance and the efficiency of modern control technologies of EU borders such as “no gate solutions”. It is therefore

¹ S. BINDER et al. “Biometric technology in “no-gate border crossing solutions” under consideration of privacy, ethical, regulatory and social acceptance.” In *Multimedia tools and applications*, 2020, pp. 1-14.

² The Entry/Exit System (EES) will be an automated IT system for registering travellers from third-countries, both short-stay visa holders and visa exempt travellers, each time they cross an EU external border. The system will register the person’s name, type of the travel document, biometric data (fingerprints and captured facial images) and the date and place of entry and exit. It will also record refusals of entry. EES will replace the current system of manual stamping of passports, which is time consuming, does not provide reliable data on border crossings and does not allow a systematic detection of over-stayers (travellers who have exceeded the maximum duration of their authorised stay).

³ ETIAS will be a largely automated IT system created to identify security, irregular migration or high epidemic risks posed by visa-exempt visitors travelling to the Schengen States, whilst at the same time facilitate crossing borders for the vast majority of travellers who do not pose such risks. Non-EU nationals who do not need a visa to travel to the Schengen area will have to apply for a travel authorisation through the ETIAS system prior to their trip. The ETIAS travel authorisation will be a mandatory pre-condition for entry to the Schengen States. It will be checked together with the travel documents by the border guards when crossing the EU border. This prior verification of visa exempt non-EU citizens will facilitate border checks; avoid bureaucracy and delays for travellers when presenting themselves at the borders; ensure a coordinated and harmonised risk assessment of third-country nationals; and substantially reduce the number of refusals of entry at border crossing points.

⁴ PERSONA, “D2.1: A study of latest and new generation no-gate crossing point solutions”, p. 17, available at

⁵ H2020 call “SU-BES01-2018-2019-2020”.

positioned as “an initiative to create a real-time decision-support system with regard to different Smart Border control technologies that empower three major stakeholder groups within the European border control sector (i.e., travellers and border control authorities & service providers) to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency. To this end, the METICOS project will develop a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and users’ acceptance of border control technologies. The proposed platform will provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision-makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions”⁶.

METICOS is/will be demonstrated in pilot implementations involving informed and consenting participants playing the role of travellers and border control staff⁷. Only adults (persons over 18 years of age) having the capacity to consent will be recruited for the purpose of the METICOS pilots. More detailed information about the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants can be found in D1.1 – “H – Requirement No. 2”.

1.2 Document objective and scope

The METICOS consortium places high value on identifying, evaluating and assessing whether the foreseen research activities and expected results will respect and promote fundamental rights in accordance and compliance with the European Convention on Human Rights⁸ and the EU’s Charter of Fundamental Rights⁹.

The METICOS platform 1) aims to measure user’s acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies 2) by using methods and tools used in the field of Big Data Analysis. Hence two main areas of concern need to be assessed from a Human Rights perspective:

1. The general aim of the METICOS platform is to explore travellers’ attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance. According to the Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA), “Travellers’ attitudes towards technologies are an important element when assessing how new measures will be received. They can help authorities forecast possible reactions and address existing fears or concerns. At the same time, travellers’ perceptions are only one element to take into account when assessing fundamental rights compliance of certain measures. Violations of fundamental rights may occur regardless of whether the individual consents or not to a certain treatment, particularly in light of limited rights awareness”¹⁰. In short, even when modern border control technologies are being accepted by its users, technologies monitored by METICOS may entail risks for fundamental rights that need to be explored. Therefore, the views of the different target

⁶ METICOS’s Description of Action, p. 2.

⁷ A first pilot was organized in Tallinn/Estonia in January 2023.

⁸ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, 1950, as amended by Protocols Nos. 11 and 14, supplemented by Protocols Nos. 1, 4, 6, 7, 12, 13 and 16.

⁹ Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 26 October 2012, 2012/C 326/02.

¹⁰ FRA, Survey in the framework of the eu-LISA pilot on smart borders – travellers’ views on and experiences of smart borders, Smart borders pilot final report - annexes, November 2015, p.307, available at https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/what-we-do/policies/borders-and-visas/smart-borders/docs/smart_borders_pilot_-_technical_report_annexes_en.pdf

groups on a number of fundamental rights aspects related to the use of border control technologies should be sought.

2. The methods and technologies being used in METICOS in order to pursue its aim stem from the field of “Big Data Analysis”. The term “Big Data” usually identifies extremely large data sets that may be analysed computationally to extract inferences about data patterns, trends, and correlations¹¹. According to the International Telecommunication Union, Big Data are “a paradigm for enabling the collection, storage, management, analysis and visualization, potentially under real-time constraints, of extensive datasets with heterogeneous characteristics”¹². The Council of Europe highlights that “the valuable insights provided by Big Data change the manner in which society can be understood and organised. Not all data processed in a big data context concern personal data and human interaction but a large spectrum of it does, with a direct impact on individuals and their rights with regard to the processing of personal data. Furthermore, since Big Data makes it possible to collect and analyse large amounts of data to identify attitude patterns and predict behaviours of groups and communities, the collective dimension of the risks related to the use of data is also to be considered”¹³. Hence, in METICOS, measures must be taken in order to prevent the potential negative impact of the use of Big Data on human dignity, human rights, and fundamental individual and collective freedoms¹⁴. In addition, several components of the METICOS platform are making use of Artificial Intelligence (AI). While AI has significant potential as a transformative technology, it also poses inherent risks. The main of those risks is bias. Therefore, it is of utmost importance to identify and mitigate the different kinds of biases that might occur in order to minimize anticipated and emergent negative impacts of the use of AI in METICOS, including threats to civil liberties and rights.

By consequence, potential impacts on human rights may derive from the overall objective of the METICOS project but also from the big data tools and AI methods being used. Table 1 below illustrates both the METICOS objective and the tools being used, the origin of human rights concerns and the potential impacts on human rights.

¹¹ Council of Europe, Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of Big Data, Strasbourg, 23 January 2017, P. 4, available at <https://rm.coe.int/CoERMPublicCommonSearchServices/DisplayDCTMContent?documentId=09000016806ebe7a>

¹² Ibidem.

¹³ Ibidem.

¹⁴ It should be noted, however, that the impacts of the METICOS platforms on the rights to privacy and data protection are analysed in a separate set of deliverables, namely D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”, due on M12 and D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32

Table 1- Human right implications deriving from METICOS objectives and tools/methods

	METICOS objective	METICOS Big Data tools and AI methods
Description	The METICOS platform measures the social acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies by EU citizens and third-country nationals.	The METICOS platform is a set of components which aim to measure user’s acceptance and efficiency of border control technologies by using methods and tools used in the field of Big Data Analysis.
Origin of human right concerns	<p>Border control checks carried out by border management authorities to verify if a person is entitled to enter the territory of an EU Member State have implications on fundamental rights.</p> <p>Moreover, the Smart Border Control technologies of which the acceptance by EU citizens and third-country nationals is envisioned to be monitored by the METICOS system include large-scale personal information systems combined with personal identity verification systems, which largely involve automated multi-biometrics-based authentication methods.</p>	The METICOS platform converts secondary statistical data coming from the different BCP databases as well as primary data provided by border staff and travellers (questionnaires, METICOS mobile & tablet applications, Twitter), into anonymized metrics and KPIs that enable evidence-based decisions for authorities and decision makers based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.
Potential impacts on Human Rights	<p>The Smart Border Control technologies of which the acceptance and efficiency are envisioned to be monitored by the METICOS platform are not as human rights and gender-neutral as they seem to be. These technologies may have unintended and unforeseen, but important, effects on the fundamental rights of travellers.</p> <p>Hence, it is important to ensure that the METICOS system takes into account the potential impacts on human rights deriving from the border control technologies of which the acceptance and efficiency are being measured.</p>	<p>The data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform in order to measure the users’ acceptance and the efficiency of border control technologies might impact the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. In addition, given that several components of the METICOS platform are making use of Artificial Intelligence, different types of bias might occur during all stages (pre-design, design & development, deployment stage) of the AI lifecycle.</p> <p>Given the work that has been carried out in the DPIA, the aim of this HRIA is not to duplicate the work conducted in D3.1 by analysing the impacts of the METICOS platform on the rights to privacy and data protection. However, as these two rights are essential to the free development of an</p>

	<p>individual's personality and identity, these rights also facilitate the enjoyment of other human rights. By consequence, any breach of privacy or data protection requirements identified in D3.1 might also have consequences on other human rights such as freedom of speech, freedom of thought, freedom of movement, prohibition of discrimination, right to liberty, conscience and religion, etc.</p> <p>In addition, this HRIA proceeds to the management of biases that might perpetuate and amplify negative impacts on travellers and border control organizations.</p>
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For both the technologies being monitored by METICOS and the big data tools/methods being used in the platform, this task (T3.3) seeks to ensure that fundamental rights are being respected.

The assessment process began at the inception of the project (M03) and will carry on throughout its lifetime (M36). It analyses all stages of the development process to gain an understanding of how each component has approached human rights intersectionality from every aspect of its development. The result will answer one question: does the proposed tool breach human rights, directly or indirectly, in any way possible?

It is important to note that, in line with the DoA, this Deliverable (D3.7) consists into a “final version of the report on human rights impact assessment”. A first version of the Human rights impact assessment was submitted on M12. In comparison with the first version, this final version addresses issues related to identification and mitigation of biases. It also takes into account the outcomes of two workshops organized in February 2023: the first workshop involved stakeholders from the sector of law and AI to discuss the implications of Artificial Intelligence on fundamental rights; the second one involved stakeholders representing travellers’ categories in order to discuss issues of representativeness during the project’s data collections.

1.3 Methodological approach

1.3.1 Aim of the human rights impact assessment

According to the DoA, this Deliverable (D3.7) should consist of the Human Right Impact Assessment of the METICOS platform.

Generally speaking, an impact assessment *“is an evaluation technique used to analyse the possible consequences of an initiative for a relevant societal concern or concerns (that is, a matter or matters of interest or importance), if this initiative could present danger to these concerns, with a view to*

supporting an informed decision on whether to deploy the initiative and under what conditions, and it constitutes – in the first place – a means to protect those societal concerns”¹⁵.

A human rights impact assessment (hereafter “HRIA”) can be defined as “*a continuous process for identifying, comprehending, evaluating and addressing the adverse effects emerging from a business project or from activities on the enjoyment of human rights enjoyment by impacted rights-holders*”¹⁶.

1.3.2 Methodology

Conducting an HRIA involves several phases or steps, all of which need to be included to ensure a comprehensive assessment:

1. Identification of the scope of the HRIA
2. Identification of the impacted groups and the impacted human rights
3. Evaluation of the impacts on human rights
4. Formulation and implementation of mitigation measures
5. Audit and review of the HRIA

This methodology is inspired from the one being proposed in the SATORI project¹⁷ which reflects both the existing literature and the R&I practice.

The figure hereunder depicts the different steps of HRIA conducted in METICOS. The audit and review of the HRIA stage run separate from the other four stages, as it applies to the entirety of the process.

¹⁵ Kloza, D, Van Dijk, N, Casiraghi, S, Vazquez Maymir, S, Roda, S, Tanas, A & Konstantinou, I 2019, 'Towards a method for data protection impact assessment: Making sense of GDPR requirements' *d.pia.lab Policy Brief*, vol. 1, no. 2019, p.1, available at https://cris.vub.be/ws/portalfiles/portal/48091346/dpialab_pb2019_1_final.pdf

¹⁶ Nora Götzmann, Tulika Bansal, Elin Wrzoncki, Cathrine Poulsen-Hansen, Jacqueline Tedaldi and Roya Høvsgaard, *Human rights impact assessment guidance and toolbox*, The Danish Institute for Human Rights, 2016, p.9, available at https://www.socialimpactassessment.com/documents/hria_guidance_and_toolbox_final_jan2016.pdf

¹⁷ SATORI, Annex 1 of Deliverable D4.1, “A Common Framework for Ethical Impact Assessment”, October 2016.

Figure 1- Methodology of METICOS' HRIA

The table below provides a summarized overview of the concrete steps of each of the stages of the HRIA conducted in this Deliverable.

Table 2 - Concrete steps of each of the stages of the HRIA

Step	Description
<p>Identify the scope of the HRIA</p>	<p>This step, based on the initial description, is taken to determine the extent of the assessment process of the METICOS project outputs.</p> <p>Potential impacts on human rights may derive from the overall objective of the METICOS project (measurement of the acceptance and efficiency of border technologies) but also from the big data tools and AI methods being used. By consequence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The scope of this HRIA should take into account potential impacts on human rights deriving from the border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform. • The scope of this HRIA should cover the “METICOS platform”, described in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.
<p>Identify the impacted groups of persons and the potentially impacted Human rights</p>	<p>This step consists of the identification of the groups of persons being impacted by the border technologies being monitored as well as by the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform.</p> <p>The goal is to list the possible human rights concerns that may be touched on.</p>
<p>Evaluate the impacts on Human Rights</p>	<p>This step is aimed at evaluating the relative importance of human rights impacts that have been determined in the previous step.</p>
<p>Formulate and implement mitigation measures</p>	<p>In this step, concrete, detailed measures (controls, safeguards, solutions, etc.) for addressing the impacts on Human Rights are proposed to minimize the negative impacts of the planned initiative and, if possible, to maximize the positive ones. Concretely, this step will result in findings and recommendations to the METICOS consortium.</p>
<p>Review and audit of the HRIA</p>	<p>The review and audit stage of the HRIA aims at ensuring independent evaluation of the HRIA process and, if necessary, of independent intervention. It especially focuses on the finalization of the HRIA, by reviewing and assessing whether the</p>

	<p>process has been successfully conducted and whether the consortium has ensured follow-ups of the relevant findings. However, the review and audit stage also plays a role during the entire HRIA process, which can steer the process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.</p> <p>Concretely, the review step will be carried out by hosting a virtual workshop with partners and external stakeholders to evaluate findings and to together weigh the impact by asking how the METICOS project will contribute to equality, dignity and autonomy, as well as to assess the foreseen impact on gender relations. In order to implement this step, two workshops were organized in February 2023: the first workshop involved stakeholders from the sector of law and AI to discuss the implications of Artificial Intelligence on fundamental rights; the second workshop involved stakeholders representing travellers' categories in order to discuss issues of representativeness during the project's data collections.</p> <p>It should also be noted that, in accordance with D1.8 "GEN - Requirement No. 11", the Ethical Board is competent to "independently and critically appraise the activities of the project undertaken in its lifetime, as well as the foreseen use of the system in an operational context after the life of the project". By consequence, the first version of this HRIA has been submitted for audit to the Ethical Board in July and August 2022. The recommendations of the Ethical Board are included in D1.10 – "GEN – Requirement No. 13".</p> <p>The final version of this HRIA was submitted to the Ethical Board in order to be audited. Therefore, two meetings with the Ethical Board were organized on March 21st and 22nd 2023. Its recommendations were taken into before submission of Deliverable to the European Commission. The minutes of these two meetings will be integrated in D1.10 – "GEN – Requirement No. 13".</p>
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1.4 Relations with other deliverables

Although this Deliverable (D3.7) is a standalone document, it is strongly interconnected with several other METICOS deliverables:

- Deliverable D1.1 is addressing the question of the participation of human beings during the research and pilots of the METICOS project. It also contains templates of the forms of consent and the information sheet.

- Deliverable D1.2 presents a list of the representatives of the Ethical Committees of the METICOS partners. The deliverable identifies the Ethical Committees of each partner of the METICOS Consortium to ensure their approval in case such approval is needed (i.e., engaging human subjects). The Ethical Committees must authorize the METICOS pilot projects before their implementation.
- Deliverable D1.6 deals with the safety measures followed for the staff involved in the METICOS project.
- Deliverable 1.7 deals with the potential misuse of data before, during, and after the implementation of the METICOS project.
- Deliverable D1.8 establishes an independent Ethical Board to monitor the ethics issues in the METICOS project and how they are handled. The members of the Ethical Board may raise any ethical or legal issue related to the METICOS project and must be consulted at least on the ethics issues raised in the ethics screening report. It is important to highlight that the HRIA conducted in this Deliverable will be submitted to the Ethical Board in order to obtain its opinion and recommendations.
- In the context of METICOS, a specific Deliverable (D3.1) is dedicated to the examination of the privacy and data protection impacts of the METICOS's platform by conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). A DPIA is “a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data⁴ by assessing them and determining the measures to address them”. By consequence, this Deliverable (D3.7) is not meant to duplicate the work conducted in D3.1 by analysing the impacts of the METICOS platform on the rights to privacy and data protection but instead will focus on identifying and mitigating the impacts of METICOS on other human rights listed in International and European instruments.

1.5 Document structure

The structure of this document is as follows:

- Section 1 provides for an introductory description of the document explaining its objectives, methodology, relation with other Deliverables and its structure.
- Section 2 defines the scope of the Human Right Impact Assessment (HRIA), which is twofold. The scope of the HRIA covers both 1) the border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform and 2) the METICOS platform itself.
- Section 3 consists into the identification of the groups of persons being impacted both by the border control technologies being monitored by the METICOS platform and by the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform. This section also aims at identifying and listing the target groups' human rights which are potentially being impacted.

- Section 4 aims at evaluating the relative importance of human rights impacts that have been determined in the previous step.
- Section 5 summarizes the mitigation measures and the recommendations having been identified.
- Section 6 provides 1) a review stage aiming to evaluate the findings of this HRIA so as to provide constructive feedback for improving the execution of the HRIA process and 2) an audit stage conducted by the Ethical Board with the aim to steer the HRIA process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.

2 Scope of the HRIA

The scope of the HRIA conducted in this Deliverable covers both 1) the border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform and 2) the METICOS platform itself, which is understood as being the combination of technologies/components presented in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

2.1 Scope 1: Identification of border control technologies being monitored by METICOS

The first scope of the HRIA covers the border control technologies intended to be monitored by the METICOS platform. In particular, the METICOS platform envisages to evaluate the efficiency and acceptance of “no-gate border crossing point solutions”. For the purposes of this Deliverable, a “No-Gate Border Crossing Point Solution” is understood to be “a method which enables travellers to cross borders without being slowed down by physical checks, based on automated risk-assessment and/or biometric verification processes”¹⁸.

The installation and use of special equipment such as self-service kiosks, ABC gates (Automated Border Control), also referred to as e-gates (electronic gates) and biometric equipment for border guards pose human rights concerns that should not be underestimated.

The table below lists examples of no-gate solutions being currently used in EU member states¹⁹.

Table 3 - No-gate solutions currently used in EU member states

Border control technology solution	Description
BorderXpress	From the information provided on BorderXpress website, by using this technology, travellers may be in the position to independently scan their identity card or passport as an intermediate step of the passport control procedure. A traveller needs to approach a kiosk and place its open passport into the scanner. The kiosk uses facial recognition technology to compare the traveller’s face to the photograph recorded on the chip in the traveller’s passport (fingerprints matching is also possible in the new version of BorderXpress) and then proceeds to border authority checks. The traveller then receives a receipt which should be presented “face to face” to a border guard at a predefined checkpoint.

¹⁸ S. BINDER et al. “Biometric technology in “no-gate border crossing solutions” under consideration of privacy, ethical, regulatory and social acceptance.” In Multimedia tools and applications, 2020, pp. 1-14.

¹⁹ The information provided in this table has been extracted from public sources, mainly the websites of airports and other cross border points as well as the websites of the providers of the technologies listed below and other publication made online. The information provided has not been cross checked with either the service providers or with the user of these technologies.

	<p>Kiosks enable the use of a two-step process that frees border control authorities from cumbersome administrative functions, such as data entry, biometric collection, etc. The first step moves administrative functions to the self-serve kiosks and a second step of document verification and supervision by border officers. The second step adds a level of security by empowering the border officer to have the final approval to allow a traveller into the country.</p>
<p>BKC-Kordon</p>	<p>According to Bancomzvjazok’s website, “The bkc-KORDON system is intended to control the flow of passengers and vehicles crossing the state border and can be applied to automobile, air, sea and pedestrian crossing points. Flexible system scalability and configuration of its parameters for individual requirements. Interoperability with external systems and sources of information (Interpol, SIS)” .</p> <p>The system "GART-1/P" works at all checkpoints: airports, railway, automobile, etc., and there are more than 2000 workplaces. Every workplace is equipped with software and hardware. On stationary workplaces "CONDOR", is used, and in mobile workplaces, the mobile terminal BPT800 is used.</p> <p>CONDOR is a full-page document reader with built-in computer for passport control:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Automatic reading and checking of documents in 3 seconds ○ Validation of passports, ID-cards, driver’s licenses, visas and other documents, including RFID-based contactless identification circuits (RFID) ○ Check listings (Stop List) and databases using on-line services ○ Recognition of text information <p>BPT800 is a portable solution for the registration and control of persons crossing security checkpoints. It provides high-quality and fast fixation of biometric data. The time for reading and processing information is up to 5 seconds. Through the use of the terminal BPT800, the passport and biometric control at any checkpoint takes no more than 20 seconds. The BPT800 Portable Terminal is made in a shock-, dust-, and waterproof enclosure. The protection degree of the case is IP67, and the protection degree of the finger scanner is IP65. The BPT800 functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ automatic readout from the machine-readable zone (MRZ) and electronic document chips (RFID) ○ recognition of text and biometric data (ICAO Document 9303) ○ fingerprint scanning (FBI) ○ verification of compliance and reliability of documents on databases ○ support for the ability to enter data manually ○ definition and fixing of GPS coordinates ○ continuous operation time – 8 hours ○ data transfer using GSM, GPRS, Wi-Fi

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ a system developers' kit (SDK) for adapting the terminal to use in existing information systems.
<p>Thales Gemalto EU EES Border Management System</p>	<p>Thales BMS Solution enables a 2-step border clearance, using biometric-enabled self-service kiosks for performing traveller pre-checks and data collection and have the Border Officer handling the border clearance. The 2-Step process consists of a registration step, performed in self-service mode by the traveller using kiosk and a border clearance final step, performed either through a manual border clearance handled by the border officer or through automated e-gates.</p> <p>Once a registered traveller goes to a stationary manual border control booth, where the information pre-enrolled at the Kiosk can be retrieved immediately thanks to a Single Identity Token (or passport or fingerprint). The Border Clearance application automatically identifies the traveller (live face capture through integrated camera) and triggers the traveller's profile. With the dedicated a web-based application the border guard can complete traveller border clearance and enrol the passenger into the EES.</p> <p>As an alternative to manual control booths, Thales Gemalto also develops ABC gates. With ABC, a traveller can pass the second step in a matter of seconds. Automation of Border control can leverage an array of different equipment, from a 2 door ABC gate or smaller one door gates.</p>
<p>PARAFE</p>	<p>PARAFE (Passage Automatisé Rapide Des Frontières Extérieures) is a self-service automated system that uses biometric technology to help travellers to cross border faster and independently in the Groupe ADP which owns and manages Parisian international airports. This service is valid for European citizens holding a biometric passport. Paris Aéroport, together with the Ministry of Home Affairs have deployed within Paris-Charles de Gaulle and Paris-Orly airports a new generation of gates which includes facial authentication technology.</p> <p>The 2 different options for this service:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facial authentication (passport, boarding pass and face) - Fingerprint authentication (passport, boarding pass and fingerprint) <p>The passenger presents himself at the entrance of an automated tunnel. He places his biometric passport, open to the photo page, on the document reader, following the instructions on the screen.</p> <p>After reading the data, the tunnel door opens. The passenger enters the tunnel, positions himself at the floor marking and follows the instructions on the screen in front of him. The passenger must be careful not to interfere with the closing of the entrance doors with his luggage. Once the authentication is completed, the exit doors open and the passenger can cross the border. On average, it takes about 20 seconds to cross the border.</p>

<p>EasyPASS</p>	<p>EasyPASS is an ABC System (e-Gates) that verifies the identity of the traveller and the validity and authenticity of their electronic travel document. Individuals must place their passport on the document reader with the data page face down. After the passport has been recognized, the door to the lane will open. In the lane, individuals must look directly at the camera located above the monitor in the exit door. The system then compares the passport photo to the live image.</p> <p>Holders of electronic passports (ePassports) from the European Union, the European Economic Area and Switzerland can use EasyPASS to enter and leave the Schengen area. Individuals must be at least 12 years old. German nationals also have the possibility of using the automated border control system with the new German identity card.</p> <p>Moreover, holders of electronic passports (ePassports) from countries that signed a mutual agreement to use automated border control procedures are now eligible to use EasyPASS-RTP to enter and leave the Schengen area – provided that they are at least 18 years old and registered with the Federal Police.</p> <p>Such agreements currently exist with the United States of America and Hong Kong Special Administrative Region Peoples Republic of China. Other third countries may follow.</p> <p>To participate in EasyPASS-RTP, individuals must visit an enrolment centre at a German airport using EasyPASS. There, they will be informed about the enrolment procedure and the data protection policy. They will then be asked to sign a form to confirm your voluntary participation in EasyPASS-RTP and consent to the storage of your personal data. Afterwards the Federal Police will check whether they meet the participation requirements by means of a questionnaire.</p> <p>Following this procedure, the Federal Police checks the validity and authenticity of the travel document and whether there are any security issues that prohibit participation in a RTP. In order to achieve this, the Federal Police checks the data against the available police information systems.</p> <p>Provided that there are no objections for security reasons, the personal data of the voluntary individuals will be stored in the EasyPASS-RTP database of the Federal Police.</p> <p>When using the ABC gate, after successful face recognition, registered travellers (RTs) from outside the EU - in contrast to the usual EasyPASS procedure - will see a special symbol and have to wait until a border guard opens the exit door. RTs then have to move forward to the monitoring booth, which is located directly behind the EasyPASS gate. An officer will then check the additional entry requirements and stamp the passport. After that procedure the border check is completed.</p>
<p>RAPID</p>	<p>The RAPID system is based on facial recognition and allows automated border crossing of passengers holding EU/EEA electronic passports.</p>

It should also be noted that the METICOS platform will be demonstrated in pilot implementations. The table below lists the technologies which are envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform during the pilots.

Table 4 - Technologies envisaged to be monitored during the pilots

Border control technology	Country of UC	Use-Case Title	Use-Case Description
Optical reader, fingerprint reader, license plate reading machine, smell dog, video endoscope, tactical mirror	Romania	Evaluation of the document verification and fingerprint reader in TIMISOARA BCP	3 citizens of German nationality (father, mother and son) present themselves for entering Romania, declaring at the border control the fact that they want to travel to Romania to visit the BRAN castle. Before entering Romania, they should pass through the document verification and fingerprint reader control. The received information will be matched with the local authority, SIS, VIS and INTERPOL databases.
Boarding pass scanner, BorderXpress kiosk	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document / non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) - Departures - No hits found	European traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Boarding pass scanner, BorderXpress kiosk, passport reader	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document / non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) - Departures - Hits found	European traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.

BorderXpress kiosk	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document /non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) - Arrivals - No hits found	European traveller is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.
BorderXpress kiosk, passport reader	Cyprus	European Traveler with biometric Travel Document / non-biometric Travel Document which contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) - Arrivals - Hits found	European traveller is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) / Third Country Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel Document - Departures - No Hits found	European / Third Country traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ)/ Third Country	European / Third Country traveller is departing from Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.

		Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel Document - Departures - Hits found	
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) / Third Country Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel Document - Arrivals - No Hits found	European / Third Country traveller is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and no hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Passport reader	Cyprus	European with non-biometric Travel Document which does not contain Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) / Third Country Traveler with biometric / non-biometric Travel Document - Arrivals - Hits found	European / Third Country traveler is arriving in Cyprus via International Airport (Pafos or Larnaca) and hits found against him/her in the available databases.
Passport reader, Ultraviolet light, national entry-exit system	Cyprus	Border checks at Larnaca and Paphos airports - arrival	Border checks at Cyprus airports, Larnaca and Paphos, are carried out by Immigration Officers of the Aliens and Immigration Unit of the Cyprus Police.

Automatic electronic entry gates (e-gates), BorderXpress interactive kiosks, Passport Reader, Ultraviolet light, Stamp machine, national entry-exit system	Cyprus	Border checks at Larnaca and Paphos airports - departure	Border checks at Cyprus airports, Larnaca and Paphos, are carried out by Immigration Officers of the Aliens and Immigration Unit of the Cyprus Police.
ABC System Control (for EU citizen with EU Biometric Passport), Manual Border Control (for TCN national), UV light, live scan for fingers, magnifier, e-passport reader	Greece	Flight from ATH to non-Schengen airport	An EU citizen and his wife, third-country national, travel from Athens airport to Dubai. The man holds an EU biometric passport. Therefore he passes through the ABC System and the woman holds a non-EU passport, so she is submitted to manual border control.
PIKO, document scanner REGULA, document control software DocCheck, Dermalog fingerprint scanner	Estonia	Fixing of the border crossing of a third-country national to the Border Control Information System (hereinafter as PIKO)	Border checks of third-country nationals
PIKO, Document Scanner REGULA, DocCheck Software	Estonia	Capturing EU/EEA/Schengen citizen's border crossing data into the PIKO	EU/EEA/Schengen citizen's border crossing check
PIKO, national and international database	Estonia	Referral of person to second-line check (step 2)	Referral of a person to the second line check in case of hits or suspicion
DIXI -01 -01UW, Mirror kits(OAD-4), Data base GART 1-P	Austria	The procedure of border control for vehicle border crossing point	The procedure of border control for vehicle border crossing point

2.2 Scope 2: Description of the METICOS system

The second scope of the HRIA conducted covers the METICOS platform which is being developed during the project. The “METICOS platform” is understood as being the combination of technologies/components listed in D3.1– “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

The purpose of the METICOS platform is to monitor the use of border control technologies with the aim of exploring both travellers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.

Given the data processing operations being carried out by the METICOS platform, human rights concerns, mostly related to privacy and data protection, must be taken into account.

The table below explains how the METICOS platform generally works. More details about the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform are available in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

Table 5 -Lifecycle of data within the METICOS platform

Processes	Description of the process
1. Statistical (anonymous) data is collected from border crossing points databases.	Statistical and anonymous data are collected from the databases of end-user organizations (border control crossing points). These statistical data are being processed by the “Universal connector” and by the “Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems ²⁰ ” in order to ensure uniform access to the various data sources based on authentication/authorization schemes and on profile-privileges and user rights.
2. Personal data are collected on Twitter (and possibly other social media sources) as well as on Blogs/Websites.	Public tweets (and possibly data originating from other social media sources ²¹) as well as online reviews on Blogs/Websites regarding acceptance of border control technologies by travelers are collected. The goal is to derive the sentiments that people have towards border control.
3. Personal data are collected directly from	Personal data are collected directly from users via the METICOS Mobile Application), the METICOS tablet Application, questionnaires and

²⁰ The Interface with Border Management Information Systems is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing statistical data that BPCs make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservices that offer information like queue lengths, average waiting times, late flights, etc and sends the data agreed with the BPC. It is important to note that the METICOS platform will not be connected with border information system like VIS, SIS or alike.

²¹ In case data originating from other social media sources than twitter are being collected during the project, this will be described and examined in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.

<p>travellers and border control staff.</p>	<p>Twitter. It should be highlighted that all primary data are collected on the basis of the consent of informed volunteers.</p>
<p>4. The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 & 3 are sent to the METICOS middleware.</p>	<p>The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 and 3 are sent to the METICOS middleware which is a software module for integration and information management of heterogeneous data sources.</p>
<p>5. In parallel with step 4, the data collected in steps 1, 2 & 3 are stored in the Data Integration Module.</p>	<p>The primary and secondary data collected in steps 1, 2 and 3 are stored in the Data Integration Module. At this stage of the project, it is envisaged to store the data processed by the METICOS platform on METICOS’s servers.</p>
<p>6. The data originating from steps 4 & 5 are being processed by the Big Data Analytics Engine.</p>	<p>The data originating from the METICOS middleware which are stored in the Data Integration Module are sent to the Big Data Analytics Engine. The Big Data Analytics Engine is composed of several sub-components: the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module, the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module and the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module. The general aim of the Big Data Analytics Engine is to uncover hidden patterns amongst attributes of gathered data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.</p>
<p>7. The data originating from step 6 are sent to the Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module.</p>	<p>The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travellers, border authorities).</p>
<p>8. The data originating from steps 6 & 7 are sent to the Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA).</p>	<p>The aim of the Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA) is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyze correlations of data generated from other METICOS components as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies.</p>
<p>9. The data originating from steps 6 & 7 are sent to the Social Toolkit Module.</p>	<p>The social sensing tool is a technology acceptance prediction system for border control technologies. The social sensing tool will analyze and estimate the activity and interactions between migrants/travelers, border staff and border control technologies for technology acceptance prediction.</p>
<p>10. The data originating from steps 8 & 9 are sent to the Personnel Front-End.</p>	<p>After the authorized border control personnel logs in to the system, the Dashboard screen is displayed. Its purpose is to display an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the</p>

	acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. Some of those metrics might include star ratings over time, speed, ease of use, emotional response. They will be displayed using graphs, pie charts and histograms that span a certain time period that may be selected by the user. The user will also have the ability to view analytics for specific checkpoints as well as aggregated analytics for all checkpoints.
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In order to have an overview of the necessity of the processing carried out by each component of the METICOS system, a questionnaire has been sent to METICOS' technology providers with the aim to understand:

1. What is being addressed by these components?
2. Why are these components being considered as a solution to these issues?

Answers to this questionnaire may be found in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”.

In addition, in order to ensure data security, the following controls are envisaged to be implemented²²:

- Statistical data originating from the border crossing points databases are anonymized before being sent to the METICOS platform. The details of the anonymization processes will be included in D3.6 – “D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.
- Logical access control verifies that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to the anonymized data originating from the border crossing points. Details on these logical access controls will be included in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.
- Logical access control verifies that only authorized researchers of the METICOS joint controllers have access to any primary or secondary data collected by the METICOS platform. Details on these logical access controls will be included in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.
- Primary and secondary data are being encrypted when stored on the METICOS servers (in the Data integration module). Details on these encryption measures will be included in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.

²² At this stage of the project, the technical system architecture and specifications of the METICOS platform have not been defined yet. Hence the following data security measures must still be confirmed. This will be reported in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.

- After having been processed by the METICOS components, all primary and secondary data are being anonymized before being sent to the Personnel Front-End. The general security goal is to avoid that non-anonymized data could be made available to authorized border control authorities or decision makers. Indeed, the overall purpose of the METICOS platform is to provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers via the End-User Front-End. Hence access to non-anonymized data to the end-users will strictly be avoided. The details of the anonymization processes will be included in D3.6 – “D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.
- Access control verifies that only authorized border control authorities and decision makers have access to the anonymized data made available via the Personnel Front-End. Details on these logical access controls will be included in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.

The figure below describes a first draft of data flow diagram enriched with security features²³.

²³ This diagram could be modified during the duration of the project. A final diagram will be included in D3.6 - “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.

Figure 2 - Data flow diagram enriched with security features

3 Identification of impacted groups of persons and impacted Human rights

3.1 Identification of the impacted groups of persons

This step consists of the identification of the groups of persons being impacted:

- 1) by the border control technologies being monitored by the METICOS platform;
- 2) by the data processing operations carried out by the METICOS platform.

3.1.1 Identification of groups of persons being impacted by border control technologies

When assessing the impacts on human rights of border control technologies which are envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform, an important step is to identify the groups of persons susceptible to be impacted by such technologies.

3.1.1.1 *Categories of travellers in the Schengen Border Code*

The primary persons or groups of persons impacted by border control technologies are of course the travellers themselves.

However, *“there are many different travellers to consider, each with local, regional and national conflicting interests and values”*²⁴. In order to categorize this multitude, from a legal point of view, a possibility is to refer to the travellers’ categories in the Schengen Borders Code²⁵ (hereafter “SBC”), which can be divided into two macro-categories: 1) Persons enjoying the Union right of free movement and 2) Third country nationals²⁶.

The main reason for this distinction is that, according to the SBC, in principle, persons enjoying the Union right of free movement, on the one hand, and third-country nationals (hereafter “TCNs”), on the other, are subject to different border control checks. Members of the first group are subject only to a “minimum check” on entry/exit of the Schengen Area, while members of the second to a more thorough one.

The table below lists which border checks, in principle, must be carried out at the external borders for each category of travellers in the SBC.

²⁴ PERSONA, “D5.2 – PERSONA textbook of assessment of no-gate crossing point solutions (1st version)”, p. 81.

²⁵ Consolidated text of Regulation (EU) 2016/399 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2016 on a Union Code on the rules governing the movement of persons across borders (Schengen Borders Code) (codification), available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0399-20190611>

²⁶ This distinction is based on article 8 of the Schengen Border Code.

Table 6 - Border checks which may be carried out at the external borders

Category of travelers in the SBC	Border checks which must be carried out at external borders according to article 8 of the SBC
Persons enjoying the right of free movement under Union law	<p>Persons enjoying the right of free movement under Union law must be subject to the following minimum systematic checks on entry and exit:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verification of the identity and the nationality of the person and of the authenticity and validity of the travel document for crossing the border, including by consulting the relevant databases, in particular: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) the SIS; b) Interpol’s Stolen and Lost Travel Documents (SLTD) database; c) national databases containing information on stolen, misappropriated, lost and invalidated travel documents. <p>For passports and travel documents containing a storage medium, the authenticity of the chip data must be checked.</p> 2. Verification that a person enjoying the right of free movement under Union law is not considered to be a threat to the public policy, internal security, public health or international relations of any of the Member States, including by consulting the SIS and other relevant Union databases. This is without prejudice to the consultation of national and Interpol databases. <p>Derogations from this rule of systematic checks of relevant databases are possible at land and sea borders subject to certain conditions following a specific procedure for notification of such derogation and risk assessment²⁷.</p>
Third-country nationals	<p>On entry and exit, third-country nationals must be subject to thorough checks as follows:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Verification of the identity and the nationality of the third-country national and of the authenticity and validity of the travel document for crossing the border, including by consulting the relevant databases, in particular: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) the SIS, b) Interpol’s SLTD database,

²⁷ See article 8, 2a of the SBC.

	<p>c) national databases containing information on stolen, misappropriated, lost and invalidated travel documents.</p> <p>For passports and travel documents containing an electronic storage medium (chip), the authenticity and integrity of the chip data shall be checked.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. Verification that the travel document is accompanied, where applicable, by the requisite visa or residence permit. 3. Verification that the person did not exceed the maximum duration of authorized stay in the territory of the Member States; 4. Verification regarding the point of departure and the destination of the third-country national concerned and the purpose of the intended stay, checking, if necessary, the corresponding supporting documents; 5. Verification that the third-country national concerned has sufficient means of subsistence for the duration and purpose of the intended stay, for his or her return to the country of origin or transit to a third country into which he or she is certain to be admitted, or that he or she is in a position to acquire such means lawfully; 6. Verification that the third-country national concerned, his or her means of transport and the objects he or she is transporting are not likely to jeopardize the public policy, internal security, public health or international relations of any of the Member States. Such verification shall include direct consultation of the data and alerts on persons and, where necessary, objects included in the SIS and other relevant Union databases, and the action to be performed, if any, as a result of an alert. This is without prejudice to the consultation of national and Interpol databases.
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The extent of the border checks that must be carried out on entry/exit of the Schengen Area depends on whether the person being controlled is a person enjoying the right of free movement under Union law or whether that person is a third-country national. Hence these those two general categories of travellers are potentially impacted differently from a Human rights’ perspective.

In addition, it derives from the reading of the SBC that these two general categories of travellers should be sub-categorized as illustrated in the table below, depending on the travel documents and EU-scale databases that must be checked. Moreover, it is very important to also consider refugees because they are particularly affected and are more vulnerable to the risks posed by border technologies.

Table 7 - Sub-categories of impacted travellers

Category of travellers in the SBC	Sub-categories of persons that may be impacted	Travel documents that must be checked	Databases against which the traveller must be checked
Persons enjoying the right of free movement under Union law	EU/EEA/CH citizens	Identity card or passport	SIS ²⁸
	Third-country nationals who are members of the	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passport • A visa, if they are nationals of a third-country subject to the visa obligation, unless they are in possession of: a valid residence 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS • EES³⁰ • VIS³¹ (if visa holder)

²⁸ The Schengen Information System (SIS) is a EU’s large-scale database aimed at ensuring a high level of security and facilitating the free movement of people within the Schengen Area through three areas of cooperation: border control, law enforcement and vehicle registration; it contains alerts on persons who may have been involved in a serious crime or may not have the right to enter or stay in the Schengen Area; on missing persons, in particular children; on certain property, such as banknotes, aircraft, boats, cars, vans, containers, firearms and identity documents, that may have been stolen, misappropriated or lost.

³⁰ The Entry/Exit System (EES) will be an automated IT system for registering travellers from third-countries, both visa holders and visa exempt travellers, each time they cross an EU external border. The system will register the person’s name, type of the travel document, biometric data (fingerprints and captured facial images) and the date and place of entry and exit. It will also record refusals of entry. EES will replace the current system of manual stamping of passports, which is time consuming, does not provide reliable data on border crossings and does not allow a systematic detection of over-stayers (travellers who have exceeded the maximum duration of their authorized stay).

³¹ The Visa Information System (VIS), is a EU’s large-scale database that supports Member States’ consular authorities in the management of applications for short-stay visas to visit or to transit through the Schengen Area; it enables the exchange of visa information and the matching of biometric data to verify the authenticity of a visa; the VIS supports the fight against fraud and facilitates checks within the territory of the Member States, assisting in the identification of any person who may not or may no longer fulfil the conditions for entry to, stay in, or residence on the territory of the Member States; as ancillary objectives, the VIS supports the asylum applications process and contributes to the prevention of threats to internal security.

	family of a EU/EEA/CH citizen ²⁹	permit or a valid residence card	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ETIAS³² (if no resident card or residence permit)
Third-country nationals	Third country nationals visa exempted (hereafter “TCNVE”)	Passport and valid residence permit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS • EES • ETIAS
	Third country nationals visa holders (TCNVH) ³³	Passport and visa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIS • EES • VIS
	Asylum seekers, Refugees, Undocumented travellers.	In several EU states, specific “refugee travel documents” may be issued. In the absence of valid documents, in a principle, a person who has crossed a border unlawfully, and who has no right to stay on the territory of the Member	EURODAC ³⁴

²⁹ To be noted that, third-country nationals who are family members of EU, EEA and CH citizens are entitled to accompany or join the EU, EEA or CH citizen for consecutive periods of up to three months per Schengen States without any conditions or formalities (except the need to have a visa for third-country nationals from a country subject to a visa requirement). When the family member travels on his/her own, the normal regime concerning the length of the short stay will (re)start to apply, as the conditions for benefiting from the facilitations concerning the free movement of the EU, EEA and CH citizens and their families are not met anymore. The previous stays performed in the area without internal border controls accompanying or joining the EU, EEA or CH citizen should not be taken into account for the sake of the calculation of the compliance with the 90/180-day rule which is applicable to the short stay only.

³² The European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS) will be a largely automated IT system created to identify security, irregular migration or high epidemic risks posed by visa-exempt visitors travelling to the Schengen States, whilst at the same time facilitate crossing borders for the vast majority of travellers who do not pose such risks. Non-EU nationals who do not need a visa to travel to the Schengen area will have to apply for a travel authorisation through the ETIAS system prior to their trip.

³³ The lists of the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement are contained in Regulation (EU) 2018/1806 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 listing the third countries whose nationals must be in possession of visas when crossing the external borders and those whose nationals are exempt from that requirement.

³⁴ The European Dactyloscopy (Eurodac) is a the EU large-scale database for the storage of fingerprints of asylum seekers and irregular migrants aged 14 and over, which enables Member States to compare the fingerprints of asylum applicants in order to see whether they have previously applied for asylum or entered the EU irregularly via another Member State, to determine the responsibility for examining an asylum application; since July 2015, Eurodac has also been used for law enforcement purposes by Member State law enforcement authorities and Europol.

		State concerned, must be apprehended and made subject to return procedures.	
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Given that the different sub-categories of travellers listed in table 7 might have very different experiences with regard to border control technologies, it is recommended that the METICOS consortium involves each of these sub-categories during the pilots.

If it is not possible to engage with all of sub-categories of travellers during the pilots, a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns (for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders – see section 6).

In addition, when presenting the pilots’ results in relation to the travellers’ acceptance level of border control technologies, these sub-categories should be differentiated (in percentages of the total of the participants).

3.1.1.2 Categories of travellers based on gender, socio-cultural factors and others

From a Human rights perspective, travellers may not be only impacted differently by border control technologies based on their belonging to a category or sub-category of travellers in the Schengen Border Code but also, potentially, on the factors listed in the table below:

Table 8 - Factors potentially impacting human rights of travellers

Factors potentially impacting human rights of travellers	Explanation
Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depending on the age group, (in particular children and elderly), experience with IT systems might be different Based on age, there is a risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Language may be a barrier to communicate with border control authorities Based on language, there is risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Gender	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Accuracy and reliability of biometrics Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Nationality	Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities

Race ³⁵ /ethnicity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accuracy and reliability of biometrics • Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Disabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disabled people could potentially face barriers when confronted to modern border control technologies and biometrics. • This factor may also lead to a risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Religious philosophical beliefs	Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Sexual orientation	Risk of stereotypes and bias on behalf of border authorities
Frequent business travellers	This category has a specific experience with border control systems.
Frequently travelling tourists	This category has a specific experience with border control systems.
Tourists that rarely travel	This category has a specific experience with border control systems.
Other	Other factors may be discussed during workshops (see section 6)

Given that the different factors listed in table 8 might potentially impact the traveller’s human rights when using border control technologies, during the pilots, it is recommended that the METICOS consortium involves participants from these diverse target groups.

If it is not possible to engage with all of these target groups during the pilots, again, a valid alternative is to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns (for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders – see section 6). This is also relevant for children since it was decided not to involve them during the pilots, as their consent to participate would not be considered as freely given (only adults over 18 with a capacity to consent will be able to participate).

In addition, when presenting the pilots’ results in relation to the travellers’ acceptance level of border control technologies, these target groups should be differentiated (in percentages of the total of the participants).

3.1.1.3 Border control staff

Aside from travellers, there are also other stakeholders to consider, particularly border guards and customs officers who need to operate the border control technologies.

³⁵ The use of the term “race” in this Deliverable does not imply an acceptance by its users of theories which attempt to determine the existence of separate human races.

However, the impacts of border control technologies on border control staff' and customs' legitimate interests (e.g. whether they fear automated technologies would take their job away or whether they think it would reduce the overall workload) should not substituted or be confused with human rights' assessment considerations³⁶. Indeed, the scope of this HRIA is to assess the impacts on human rights, not on other legitimate interests.

Having clarified this important distinction, it is however important to get the views of border control staff on the impacts that the technologies they are operating might have on travellers' human rights.

By consequence, it is recommended to the METICOS consortium to give voice to the border control' staff opinions and views on the impacts that border control technologies might have on travellers' human rights (for example, during workshops with partners and – see section 6).

3.1.2 Identification of groups of persons being impacted by the METICOS platform

In order to identify the groups of persons being impacted by each component of the METICOS platform, a questionnaire has been sent to METICOS' technology providers. Answers are reported in the table hereunder.

³⁶ Even though, it could be argued that such concerns might fall in the scope of application of Article 15 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (Freedom to choose an occupation and right to engage in work).

Table 9 - Target groups impacted by each component of the METICOS platform

Component/ Technology	Description	Border control staff	Travellers	Other
Data Integration Module	METICOS Common Data Management Engine (CDME) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way. All the exchanged information will be translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all METICOS components use them.	N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.	N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.	
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Unstructured Data	The aim of the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module is to gather and analyse unstructured data from different sources (historical unstructured data, real-time unstructured, data gathered at pilot sites, free text in questionnaires, tweets and social media). Hence, the engine will be capable of extracting data from social media (twitter, reviews, blogs...) in a real-time automated way and storing it with the aim of further processing the data. The engine will include the functionality of sentiment detection and context detection (most important words, clustering) of social media data (twitter, reviews, blogs, etc.) in order to capture the general acceptance and social acceptance of SBC technologies. The user will be able to see most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that people are tweeting about regarding smart border control technologies.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Structured Data	The Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data will and analyse structured data coming from several sources (historical data, real-time data gathered at pilot sites, questionnaires ...). The ADME component at the end of the project will uncover hidden	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are	

	patterns amongst attributes of gathered structured data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.	consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	
Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module.	The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travelers, border authorities).	No	Yes	
Cross-sectorial (big) data analysis mechanisms	The purpose of the Cross-Sectorial Big Data Analysis (CS-BDA) Mechanisms module is to infer the acceptance of a BCP or technology by aggregating and analysing data from different sources, locations and formats. It accepts the outputs of other components (ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data, and others). The output of the CS-BDA component will be fed in the DTVA component.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	N/A: Since this component is a backend module, the functionalities provided by this component are consumed by the DTVA. Therefore, no target groups are addressed.	
Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit	The aim of Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module (DTVA) is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyse correlations of data generated from other METICOS components as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies. It will provide a platform where the outputs from the ADME for Structured Data, ADME for Unstructured Data and CS-BDA modules will be visualised and presented.	The border control authorities will be impacted from the output of this component in the following way: This target group will be able to see and interact with a dashboard where the output of multiple METICOS components will be demonstrated and thus draw conclusions for	The anonymized data is related to the use of border control technologies by travellers	

		the general acceptance of SBC technologies per BCP but also generally (aggregated view)		
METICOS Middleware	All information coming from the data sources will be sent to the middleware module for processing and/or storage. That information will be used to perform data mining and analytics about the passengers' perception of the technologies used at border checkpoints.	N/A: Module is not targeting a user group or role. 2) The whole system is affected by the Meticos Middleware	N/A: Module is not targeting a user group or role. 2) The whole system is affected by the Meticos Middleware	
Personel Front-End	After the authorized border control personnel logs in to the system, the Dashboard screen is displayed. Its purpose it to display an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. Some of those metrics might include star ratings over time, speed, ease of use, emotional response. They will be displayed using graphs, pie charts and histograms that span a certain time period that may be selected by the user. The user will also have the ability to view analytics for specific checkpoints as well as aggregated analytics for all checkpoints.	Yes: Users (personnel) interact with the system through Front-End	The anonymized data is related to the use of border control technologies by travellers	Anonymized data will be beneficial to societal research and decision making
Border Checkpoint and Mobile App for passengers	The passengers will be able to see the airport's latest news, information about their flights and airport facilities, give reactions (e.g. smileys, star ratings), answer questionnaires and provide feedback through the METICOS tablet application. These functionalities can also be accessed from the passengers' personal devices by downloading a mobile application to their cellphone. This application also enables use of the platform by people with disabilities through the use of audio based on WCAG 2.0 (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines).	Yes: Quality of the input data is important for border control authorities to obtain relevant anonymized data through the Personel Front-End.	Yes: Passengers interact with the system through this component Elder people may be not willing to participate, especially if they travel alone	

<p>Universal Connector</p>	<p>The component offers a uniform access to various data sources. It offers a standard API to access data from different data sources and hides their technological implementation details. The component has multiple connector modules that support various connection types.</p>	<p>N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.</p>	<p>N/A: This is an internal component. The user have no access to it.</p>	
<p>Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems</p>	<p>The Interface with Border Management Information Systems is a term used to indicate the mechanisms for accessing statistical data that BPCs make available in order to be used in the technology acceptance algorithms. This mechanism may be files that are published to a FTP/Web server or webservices that offer information like queue lengths, average waiting times, late flights, etc and sends the data agreed with the BPC. It is important to note that the METICOS platform will not be connected with border information system like VIS, SIS or alike.</p>	<p>Yes: The target group for this component are Border and Customs authorities</p>	<p>No: Since this is an integration component, it not anticipated to affect any other target groups.</p>	
<p>Social Toolkit</p>	<p>The social sensing tool is a technology acceptance prediction system for border control technologies. The social sensing tool will analyze and estimate the activity and interactions between migrants/travelers, border staffs and border control technologies for technology acceptance prediction. The Social Toolkit Module is composed of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The socio-cultural framework; • Automated tools for assessing threshold <p>The socio-cultural framework module (SCFM) will allow the METICOS platform to assess the main reasons behind underlying circumstances that can affect the process of individuals with different sociocultural backgrounds trying to pass through given BCP technologies. It will make use of multiple parameters, such as</p>	<p>Yes: this component targets travellers and border staff), their interactions with the technology, response and waiting time while using technology and other relevant data attributes.</p>	<p>Yes: this component targets travellers and border staff), their interactions with the technology, response and waiting time while using technology and other relevant data attributes.</p>	

	<p>age, gender, social status, education, professional status, cultural background, lifestyle, native language, gestures etc.</p> <p>The Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) will define a specific threshold for each BCP technology when dealing with non-EU travellers. It will include parameters related to the overall complexity of the device/technology used, the level of interaction with different users, response time, the level of flexibility, level of support from border authorities etc., along with context-based data to adjust the threshold accordingly.</p>			
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From table 9, it derives that the target groups of the METICOS platform can be divided into two main categories: data subjects and recipients.

- The data subjects of the data processed by the METICOS platform are travellers and border staff about which data is being collected.
- The recipients of the data processed by the METICOS platform are: border staff members, researchers and decision-makers who are entitled to view the aggregated data via the Personnel Front-End and the Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit.

Consequently, in the METICOS' HRIA, the impacts on the human rights of travellers and border staff about which data is being collected should be analyzed. These two categories of target groups have already been sub-categorized in section 3.1.1.

3.2 Identification of impacted Human rights

Having now identified the target groups of both the border control technologies and the METICOS platform, this section is dedicated to identifying and listing the target groups' human rights which are potentially being impacted.

3.2.1 Human Rights that may be impacted by the border technologies

In order to identify and list the travellers' human rights which might potentially be impacted by the border control technologies envisaged to be evaluated, we proceeded to a horizon scanning of related European projects.

For each related European project, the table hereunder lists the impacted human rights which were identified in the ethical work that was carried out³⁷.

Table 10 - Horizon scanning of human rights impacted by border control technologies

Name and description of project	Identified impacted Human rights
<p>SMILE is a research project, based on biometric technologies, aimed to achieve an automated, rapid and highly secure self-service clearance process, such that increasing passenger throughput does not compromise border control reliability.</p> <p>A summary of the fundamental ethical concerns listing the impacted human rights is to be found</p>	<p>Human dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to the integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (Art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) – Equality before the law (Art. 20 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Respect cultural, religious and linguistic diversity (Art. 22 CFR) - Equality between men and women (Art. 23 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24 CFR) - Rights of the</p>

³⁷ In the table below, references are made to relevant articles of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (hereafter "CFR").

in “D8.6 - Ethics Manual and Guidelines for land BCPS” ³⁸ .	elderly (Art. 25 CFR) - Integration of persons with disabilities (Art. 26 CFR)
<p>PERSONA project provides a unified and tailored Impact Assessment Method for No-Gate Crossing Point Solutions capable of appropriately evaluating border controlling technologies and of ensuring that these solutions meet the requirements and expectations of governments, LEAS, and border crossing individuals.</p> <p>A summary of impacted human rights is to be found in “D1.3 - PERSONA benchmark for the assessment process”³⁹.</p>	Human dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Prohibition of inhuman or degrading treatment (Art. 4 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) - Protection in the event of removal, expulsion or extradition (Art. 19 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24) - Rights of the elderly (Art. 25 CFR) - Integration of persons with disabilities (Art. 26 CFR)
<p>TRESPASS aims to develop, demonstrate and validate a single cohesive risk-based border management concept for air, maritime and land border crossing points.</p> <p>TRESPASS identifies “ethical, legal and societal aspects” in “D9.6 - Typology of ethical, legal and societal issues of risk-based screening”⁴⁰. This document does not contain a comprehensive list of impacted human rights. Nonetheless, these could be deduced.</p>	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Right to good administration (Art. 41 CFR) - Right of access to documents (Art. 42 CFR) - Freedom of movement (Art. 45 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)
<p>MIRROR aims to produce technical tools to help assess the perceptions and misperceptions of Europe and individual European countries of persons migrating to Europe. By understanding these perceptions and misperceptions, it is hoped the border agencies can adopt a more predictive-oriented approach to their activities</p>	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to freedom of expression (Art. 11 CFR) - Right to freedom of Assembly and Association (Art. 12 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)

³⁸ SMILE, “D8.6 - Ethics Manual and Guidelines for land BCPS”, p.12, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5beee3af9&applied=PPGMS>

³⁹ PERSONA, “D1.3 - PERSONA benchmark for the assessment process”, p. 44, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5cef1ac5c&applied=PPGMS>

⁴⁰ TRESPASS, “D9.6 - Typology of ethical, legal and societal issues of risk-based screening”, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5d55dc0ec&applied=PPGMS>

<p>and manage migration flows, expectations, as well as their resources better.</p> <p>A summary of impacted human rights is to be found in “D3.2 - Human Rights Implications Checklist”⁴¹.</p>	
<p>PROTECT develops a multimodal biometric solution for identity confirmation “on the move” of travellers with the aim to facilitate the Schengen Area external cross-border movements. The system should, therefore, process various “emerging” biometric modalities which could be processed in a contactless-way.</p> <p>A summary of impacted human rights is to be found in “D2.2 - Legal framework of biometric border control”⁴².</p>	<p>Right to dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (Art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR), Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) - Protection in the event of removal, expulsion or extradition (Art. 19 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy (Art. 47 CFR).</p>

The human rights listed in table 10 might be impacted by border control technologies envisaged to be monitored by the METICOS platform. These technologies are listed in tables 3 and 4. Most of these technologies share some common objectives: 1) they aim to confirm the identity of the holder of an eDocument through biometric verification and 2) they query border control databases to determine eligibility of border crossing according to the pre-defined rules.

By consequence, the main reasons explaining why these human rights are being impacted are:

- 1) the collection and processing of biometric data (facial image, fingerprints) to verify the identity of the document’s holder;
- 2) the processing of personal data in centralized IT systems (SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc) for border control management.

In the context of the METICOS platform, these legal impacts should be analysed since that the purpose of the platform is, amongst others, to measure the acceptance of border technologies by its users. However, social or technology acceptance differs from legal acceptability. As emphasized by the Fundamental Rights Agency (FRA), “Travellers’ attitudes towards technologies are an important element when assessing how new measures will be received. they can help authorities to forecast possible reactions and address existing fears or concerns. At the same time, travellers’ perceptions are only one element to take into account when assessing fundamental rights compliance of certain

⁴¹ MIRROR, “D3.2 - Human Rights Implications Checklist”, p.18, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5d219840d&appId=PPGMS>

⁴² PROTECT, “D2.2 - Legal framework of biometric border control”, p. 11, available at <https://emdesk.eu/shared/5ac3e931b9b0c-4bb5b487e91d73af0a5d898b3f898679>

measures. Violations of fundamental rights may occur regardless of whether the individual consents or not to a certain treatment, particularly in light of limited rights awareness”⁴³.

Hence, within METICOS, the objective of the analysis of the human right’s implications of border control technologies is to complement the social acceptance studies (conducted in WP5) in order to ensure that the collection of primary data through questionnaires as well as via the METICOS mobile & tablet applications reflect the human rights’ concerns deriving from the use of these technologies. The aim is to seek the views of the different target groups on a number of fundamental rights aspects related to the use of border control technologies.

3.2.2 Human Rights that may be impacted by the METICOS platform

In addition to the travellers’ human rights that may be impacted by the border technologies envisaged to be monitored, other human rights may be impacted by the big data tools and methods being used by the METICOS platform.

As a reminder, the purpose of the METICOS platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes toward border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.

In order to fulfill its purpose, the METICOS platform processes different sets of data:

1. Primary Data: Primary data is the type of data that is collected directly from informed and consented “users” (travellers and border guards) during the METICOS project activities and during pilots at the Border Control Points. Such primary data originates from:
 - a. Questionnaires addressing specific questions about border crossing points, their control routines and technologies used;
 - b. Twitter: After crossing the border in the METICOS pilot site, the user is posting a tweet in the using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag;
 - c. METICOS Mobile Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a mobile application;
 - d. METICOS Tablet Application: The user answers questions related to border control processes (time, queue length, performance, etc.) via a tablet application.

⁴³ FRA, Survey in the framework of the eu-LISA pilot on smart borders – travellers’ views on and experiences of smart borders, Smart borders pilot final report - annexes, November 2015, p.307, available at https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/default/files/what-we-do/policies/borders-and-visas/smart-borders/docs/smart_borders_pilot_-_technical_report_annexes_en.pdf

2. Secondary data: Secondary data is the type of data that is relevant to METICOS, but has been collected in the past. Such data is already available to use in the context of the project from existing sources. Such secondary data originates from:
 - a. Statistical data originating from border crossing points' databases;
 - b. Twitter: The aim is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.
 - c. Online reviews of BCPs on blogs/websites

By consequence of these data processing operations, the main human rights that might be potentially impacted by the METICOS platform are the rights to privacy (art. 7 CFR) and to data protection (art. 8 CFR). Given the importance of the rights to privacy and data protection for the METICOS platform, a specific Deliverable (D3.1) was dedicated to conducting a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). A DPIA is “a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR. In other words, a DPIA is a process for building and demonstrating compliance.”⁴⁴

Given the work that has been carried out in the DPIA, the aim of this HRIA is not to duplicate the work conducted in D3.1 by analysing the impacts of the METICOS platform on the rights to privacy and data protection. However, as these two rights are essential to the free development of an individual's personality and identity, these rights also facilitate the enjoyment of other human rights⁴⁵. By consequence, any breach of privacy or data protection requirements identified in D3.1 might also have consequences on other human rights such as freedom of speech, freedom of thought, freedom of movement, prohibition of discrimination, right to liberty, conscience and religion, etc.

Moreover, in the beginning of the project, we identified that other human rights may be impacted by the METICOS platform as a consequence of:

- 1) The potential use of Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) during pilots in order to detect the participants' acceptance;
- 2) The potential collection of data from participants' travel documents;
- 3) The potential connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc;

⁴⁴ See Article 29 Working Party, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP 248 rev.01, adopted on 4 April 2017, last revised and adopted on 4 October 2017

⁴⁵ The General Assembly, the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights and special procedure mandate holders have recognised privacy as a gateway to the enjoyment of other rights (UNGA resolution 68/167, A/HRC/13/37; Human Rights Council resolution 20/8).

Finally, several impacts on fundamental rights may also be caused by potential biases that may occur in the development lifecycle of components of the METICOS platform that are using Artificial Intelligence. Such biases may occur in the algorithms and models, and in the datasets upon which the components are built.

The table 11 below lists which human rights may be impacted by the METICOS platform.

Table 11 - Identified human right impacts of the METICOS platform

Origin of the impact	Human right(s) being impacted	Explanation
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the travellers' data within the METICOS platform such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deanonymization of the primary and secondary data being processed by the METICOS platform. • Illegitimate access to primary and secondary data processed by the METICOS platform. 	<p>Human dignity (Art. 1 CFR) - Right to the integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Prohibition of inhuman or degrading treatment (Art. 4 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Freedom of thought, conscience and religion (art. 10 CFR) - Freedom of expression and information (art. 11 CFR) - Equality before the law (Art. 20 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Respect cultural, religious and linguistic diversity (Art. 22 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)</p>	<p>In case of data breaches in the METICOS platform, illegitimate recipients might take unfair individual decisions towards METICOS users. Such decisions might impact different human rights, depending on the concrete circumstances.</p>
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the border guard staff's data within the METICOS platform.</p>	<p>Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Freedom to choose an occupation and right to engage in work (Art. 15 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR)</p>	<p>In case of breaches of border guard's data in the METICOS platform, the staff may be discriminated by their employers.</p>
<p>Potential use of Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) during pilots in order to detect the travellers' acceptance.</p>	<p>Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR)</p>	<p>Using Facial Emotion Recognition cameras during the pilots might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to</p>

		privacy and data protection of travellers.
The potential collection of data from the travellers' documents by non-authorized border staff ⁴⁶ .	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR)	The collection of data directly from travel documents by non-authorized border staff might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.
The potential connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, etc ⁴⁷ .	Right to the integrity of the person (Art. 3 CFR) - Right to liberty and security (Art. 6 CFR) - Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) - Protection in the event of removal, expulsion or extradition (Art. 19 CFR) - Freedom of movement (Art. 45 CFR) - Right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial (Art. 47 CFR)	The connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, etc might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such interferences might have impacts on other fundamental rights depending on the concrete circumstances.
Lack of transparency of the data collection from Twitter and other social media.	Respect for private and family life (Art. 7 CFR) - Protection of personal data (Art. 8 CFR) - Freedom of expression and information (art. 11 CFR).	Retrieving any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and mining the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such a data processing could also potentially lead to an interference with the freedom of expression.

⁴⁶ As explained in section 5, because of the ethical risks, it was decided to finally not collect data directly from travel documents.

⁴⁷ As explained in section 5, because of the ethical risks, it was decided to finally not connect the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES.

<p>Potential undercoverage bias due to target groups not adequately represented in the METICOS pilots' and research' samples.</p>	<p>Right to asylum (Art. 18 CFR) – Equality before the law (Art. 20 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Respect cultural, religious and linguistic diversity (Art. 22 CFR) - Equality between men and women (Art. 23 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24 CFR) - Rights of the elderly (Art. 25 CFR) - Integration of persons with disabilities (Art. 26 CFR)</p>	<p>The research results of the METICOS project might be biased in case of insufficient representation of the different impacted groups of persons identified in section 3.</p> <p>Such biases might have impacts on different human rights depending on the concrete circumstances.</p>
<p>Lack of identification and mitigation of biases that might occur in the development lifecycle of components/technologies of METICOS which are based on Artificial Intelligence.</p>	<p>Equality before the law (Art. 20 CFR) - Non-discrimination (Art. 21 CFR) - Respect cultural, religious and linguistic diversity (Art. 22 CFR) - Equality between men and women (Art. 23 CFR) - Rights of the child (Art. 24 CFR) - Rights of the elderly (Art. 25 CFR) - Integration of persons with disabilities (Art. 26 CFR)</p>	<p>Technology based on AI has broader impacts on fundamental rights than traditional software.</p> <p>Data sets, models and algorithms used by AI systems may suffer from the inclusion of bias. The continuation of such biases could lead to unintended (in)direct prejudice and discrimination against certain groups or people, potentially exacerbating prejudice and marginalisation.</p>

4 Evaluation of the impacts on human rights

4.1 Evaluation of impacts on human rights deriving from border control technologies

Within METICOS, the objective of the analysis of the human rights' implications of border control technologies is to complement the social acceptance studies (conducted in WP5) in order to ensure that the collection of primary data through questionnaires as well as via the METICOS mobile & tablet applications reflect the human rights' concerns deriving from the use of these technologies. The aim is to seek the views of the different target groups on a number of fundamental rights aspects related to the use of border control technologies.

4.1.1 Impact of the processing of biometric data in travel documents

4.1.1.1 Description of the types of biometrics included in travel documents

According to the Article 29 Working Party, "Biometric data changes irrevocably the relation between body and identity, because they make the characteristics of the human body 'machine-readable' and subject to further use"⁴⁸. This is the main reason justifying that biometric data is considered as being particularly sensitive by EU data protection norms⁴⁹.

Over the years, border control has become smarter with eDocuments using biometric technology as a key element, enabling authorities to verify that a traveller is who they claim to be and that they are authorised to enter a country.

The table 12 below lists the type of biometrics contained in each type of travel document as well as the categories of persons that are exempted from providing fingerprints.

Table 12 - Types of biometrics included in eDocuments and exemptions

Type of eDocument	Biometrics included	Exempted persons
ID card ⁵⁰	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facial image two fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children under the age of 12 years may be exempt from

⁴⁸ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 3/2012 on developments in biometric technologies, adopted on 27th April 2012, WP193, p.4.

⁴⁹ See article 9 of the GDPR and article 10 of the Directive (EU) 2016/680 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data by competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection or prosecution of criminal offences or the execution of criminal penalties, and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Council Framework Decision 2008/977/JHA.

⁵⁰ The inclusion of biometrics in ID cards is regulated by article 3 of Regulation (EU) 2019/1157 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on strengthening the security of identity cards of Union citizens and of residence documents issued to Union citizens and their family members exercising their right of free movement.

		<p>the requirement to give fingerprints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 6 years shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints. • Persons in respect of whom fingerprinting is physically impossible shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints⁵¹.
ePassport ⁵²	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facial image • Two fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 12 years are exempted to provide fingerprints. • Persons, where fingerprinting is physically impossible are exempted⁵³.
Residence permit ⁵⁴	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facial image • Two Fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The capture of fingerprints is compulsory as of six years of age. • Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically impossible are exempted.
Schengen Visa ⁵⁵	The visa stickers do not contain any biometric traits. However, once an application is found	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 12 are exempted to provide fingerprints.

⁵¹ According to article 4, §3 of Regulation (EU) 2019/1157, “Member States shall issue an identity card having a validity of 12 months or less where it is temporarily physically impossible to take fingerprints of any of the fingers of the applicant”.

⁵² The inclusion of biometrics in ePassports is regulated by article 1 of the consolidated version of Council regulation No 2252/2004 of 13 December 2004 on standards for security features and biometrics in passports and travel documents issued by Member States.

⁵³ According to article 2b of the consolidated version of Council regulation No 2252/2004: “Where fingerprinting of the designated fingers is temporarily impossible, Member States shall allow the fingerprinting of the other fingers. Where it is also temporarily impossible to take fingerprints of any of the other fingers, they may issue a temporary passport having a validity of 12 months or less”.

⁵⁴ The inclusion of biometrics in residence permits is regulated by articles 4a and 4b of the consolidated version of Council Regulation (EC) No 1030/2002 of 13 June 2002 laying down a uniform format for residence permits for third-country nationals.

⁵⁵ The inclusion of biometrics in the VIS is regulated by article 13 of the consolidated version of Regulation (EC) No 810/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 establishing a Community Code on Visas (Visa Code).

	<p>admissible as set out in the Visa Code, the visa authority creates the application file by entering data into the Visa Information System (VIS) including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facial image⁵⁶ • 10 fingerprints 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically impossible are exempted. If the fingerprinting of fewer than 10 fingers is possible, the maximum number of fingerprints shall be taken.
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As illustrated in the table above, the type of biometrics included in the majority of the EU travel documents consist of two fingerprints and the holder's facial image. The use of these biometrics could have a significant impact on the dignity, privacy and the right to data protection of vulnerable people such as young children, elderly people and persons physically unable to complete the enrolment process successfully. This is why regulatory texts contain some exemptions as regards the requirement to provide fingerprints. Indeed, appropriate safeguards must be in place against the risks of stigmatization or discrimination of those individuals either because of their age or because of their inability to enroll. In any case, "specific safeguards (such as appropriate fallback procedures) should be implemented so as to ensure the respect for human dignity and fundamental freedoms of any individual that is unable to complete the enrolment process successfully and thereby avoid burdening such individual with the imperfections of the technical system"⁵⁷.

Moreover, factors such as class, ability, gender, skin colour and age – and the intersection of these factors – can negatively influence someone's ability to be recognized by the biometric apparatus.

In addition, for all categories of persons, there are privacy risks that should be taken into account when relying on fingerprints and facial recognition. These risks are summarized in the next two sub-sections.

4.1.1.2 Main privacy risks of fingerprints

Fingerprint recognition is among the oldest, most widely studied and most extensively deployed biometric systems. Identification by fingerprints has been used for more than 100 years in law enforcement for both verification and identification tasks. It is founded in the fact that every individual has unique fingerprints showing specific characteristics that can be measured in order to decide if a fingerprint matches against an enrolled sample. Enrolment requires the individual to be physically present as well as, depending on the expected use, well trained personnel in order to ensure good

⁵⁶ Although the VIS does not collect facial images at the moment, the Council has proposed an amendment for the proposed VIS Regulation suggesting that the visa procedure and the VIS should benefit from the technology developments related to facial image recognition and taking live facial images as part of the short stay visa procedure. See Council of the European Union, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EC) No 767/2008, Regulation (EC) No 810/2009, Regulation (EU) 2017/2226, Regulation (EU) 2016/399, Regulation XX/2018 [Interoperability Regulation], and Decision 2004/512/EC and repealing Council Decision 2008/633/JHA— Presidency compromise proposals regarding the recitals, 13799/18, 5 November 2018.

⁵⁷ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 3/2012 on developments in biometric technologies, adopted on 27th April 2012, WP193, p.15.

data quality. Fingerprint capture is not a trivial task. In that sense matching accuracy will depend on the image quality in relation to the image technique. Even if it not in principle a highly invasive method, it can be felt as such because it comes with the negative image of being treated as a suspect due to its common use in law enforcement.

According to the Article 29 Working Party⁵⁸, there are data protection concerns associated with the use of fingerprints that can be briefly described as follows:

- **Accuracy:** Even though fingerprints eventually present a high accuracy rate, this can be challenged due to limitations related to the information (low quality of the data or non-consistent acquisition process) or representation (features selected or quality of the extraction algorithms) issues. This can lead to false rejection or false matches.
- **Impact:** The irreversibility of the process can reduce the possibility of the individual of exercising their rights or to reverse decisions adopted based on a false identification. The reliance on the accuracy of fingerprinting can make possible mistakes harder to rectify, leading to far reaching consequences for individuals. This needs to be taken into account when the proportionality of the processing in relation to the specific decision to be taken based on the fingerprints is assessed. It should be also mentioned that lack of security measures can lead to identity theft that can have a strong impact on the individual.
- **Linkability:** fingerprints provide the potential for misuse as the data can be linked with other databases. This possibility of linking up to other databases can lead to uses non compatible with the original purposes.
- **Processing of sensitive data:** According to some studies, fingerprint images can reveal ethnical information of the individual.
- **Further purposes or purposes of processing:** Central storage of data, especially on large databases, implies risks associated with data security, linkability and function creep. This allows, in absence of safeguards, the use of the fingerprints for purposes different than those that initially justified the processing.
- **Revocability:** fingerprint data are very stable with time and should be considered irrevocable. A fingerprint template may be revoked under certain conditions.

4.1.1.3 Main privacy risks of facial image

The face, like fingerprints, has been used extensively as a source of biometric data for a number of years. More recently it is not only identity that can be determined from a face but physiological and psychological characteristics such as ethnic origin, emotion and wellbeing.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*, pp.20-21.

The ability to extract this volume of data from an image and the fact that a photograph can be taken from some distance without the knowledge of the data subject demonstrates the level of data protection issues which can arise from such technologies.

According to the Article 29 Working Party⁵⁹, data protection risks associated with the use of facial recognition systems can be described as follows:

- **Accuracy:** If the quality of images cannot be guaranteed there is a risk that the accuracy will be compromised. If a face is not captured (obscured by hair or a hat) it is clear that a matching or categorisation cannot take place without a high degree of error. Pose and illumination variations remain a big challenge for facial recognition, highly affecting the accuracy.
- **Consent & Transparency:** A data protection risk not seen in many other types of biometric data processing is the fact that images can be captured and processed from a range of viewpoints, environmental conditions and without the knowledge of the data subject.
- **Further purpose or purposes of processing:** Once captured, whether legitimately or unlawfully, digital images can be easily shared or copied for processing in different systems from those which they were originally intended.
- **Processing of sensitive data:** Processing of biometric data could be used to determine sensitive data, in particular those with visual cues such as race, ethnic group or perhaps a medical condition.

4.1.1.4 Dealing with the impact of biometrics in travel documents within METICOS

Within METICOS, in order to reflect the human rights' concerns deriving from the use of biometrics in travel documents, it is recommended to:

- Involve participants holding the different types of travel documents listed in table 12 during the METICOS pilots. This might be achieved by involving the target groups identified in table 7 of this Deliverable.
- Involve participants of different:
 - a) age-groups, including elderly (children will not be involved in the pilots but a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns, for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders – see section 6);
 - b) gender;
 - c) race /ethnicity;
 - d) nationality;
 - e) religious philosophical beliefs

⁵⁹ Ibid., pp. 22-23..

- f) health condition, in particular disabilities.

This might be achieved by involving the target groups being identified in table 8 of this Deliverable.

- In the questionnaires being circulated (as well as in the questions asked via the METICOS mobile and tablet applications), it is recommended to include questions such as:
 - Do you believe that the storage of biometrics in travel documents is humiliating (intrusive to your dignity)?
 - Do you believe that the storage of biometrics in travel documents is intrusive to your privacy?
 - Do you believe it is important to be informed on why your biometric identifiers are stored on travel documents?
 - Do you consider that the storage of the facial image on travel documents is important to secure borders?
 - Do you consider is the storage of fingerprints in travel documents is important to secure borders?
 - How comfortable do you feel with facial image being stored in travel documents?
 - How comfortable do you feel with fingerprints being stored in travel documents?
 - Which biometrics are you more in favour of to be stored in travel documents (facial image or fingerprints)?
 - Would you prefer travel documents not to contain any biometrics?
 - For fingerprints, how many fingers' templates do you consider proportionate to be stored on travel documents?
 - Do you trust the reliability of the fingerprints stored on your travel document?
 - Do you trust the reliability of the facial image stored on your travel document?
 - Do you believe that biometrics are securely stored in travel documents?
 - Under what age do you consider that fingerprints should not be stored on travel documents?
 - Under what age do you consider that facial image should not be stored on travel documents?
 - Do you believe that the storage of the facial image is discriminatory on grounds of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation?
 - Do you believe that the storage of the fingerprints is discriminatory on grounds of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation?

The aim of this recommendation is not to provide a final list of questions to be included in the questionnaires. This draft list only serves as a recommendation for WP5 partners.

- If the questionnaires being circulated (as well as the questions asked via the METICOS mobile and tablet applications) aim to evaluate the acceptance of iris recognition, it should be recalled to the respondents that iris is not a type of biometrics being currently allowed to be stored in eDocuments according to applicable regulations. This remark is also valid for any questions related to the user's acceptance of other types of biometrics than facial image and fingerprints.

4.1.2 Impact of the use of large-scale IT systems

4.1.2.1 Description of the EU large-scale IT systems

The large-scale EU large-scale databases presently include: the second-generation Schengen Information System (SIS II), the Visa Information System (VIS), the European Dactyloscopy (Eurodac), and the more recent Entry-Exit System (EES), European Criminal Records Information System for Third Country Nationals (ECRIS-TCN) and European Travel Information and Authorisation System (ETIAS).

In a nutshell, “the SIS allows competent authorities in the EU to issue and consult alerts on missing or wanted objects and people. The VIS supports Member States’ consular authorities in the management of applications for short-stay visas to visit or to transit through the Schengen Area. The Eurodac supports competent authorities in determining the responsibility for examining an asylum application. In the near future, the EES will electronically register the time and place of entry and exit of third-country nationals, both those requiring a visa and those who are visa-exempt, admitted for a short stay, other than those refused to entry. The ECRIS-TCN will allow Member States’ authorities to identify which other Member States hold criminal records on the third-country nationals or stateless persons being checked. The ETIAS will constitute a pre-travel authorisation system for visa-exempt travellers, the key function of which is to verify if a third-country national meets entry requirements before travelling to the Schengen Area, enabling pre-travel assessment of irregular migration, security or public health risks”⁶⁰.

The table 13 below lists the types of biometrics being processed in each large-scale IT system as well as the persons being exempted, when applicable.

Table 13 - Type of biometrics included in each large-scale IT system

IT database	Biometrics included	Exempted persons
SIS	Palm prints, fingerprints, facial images and DNA samples.	N/A
VIS	Facial image ⁶¹ and data relating to the five fingerprints of the index, middle finger, ring finger, little finger and the thumb from the right	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Children under the age of 12 are exempted to provide fingerprints. Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically

⁶⁰ J. P. Burges and D. Kloza, “Border control and new technologies – addressing Integrated Impact Assessment”, 2021, p. 121.

⁶¹ Although the VIS does not collect facial images at the moment, the Council has proposed an amendment for the proposed VIS Regulation suggesting that the visa procedure and the VIS should benefit from the technology developments related to facial image recognition and taking live facial images as part of the short stay visa procedure. See Council of the European Union, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EC) No 767/2008, Regulation (EC) No 810/2009, Regulation (EU) 2017/2226, Regulation (EU) 2016/399, Regulation XX/2018 [Interoperability Regulation], and Decision 2004/512/EC and repealing Council Decision 2008/633/JHA— Presidency compromise proposals regarding the recitals, 13799/18, 5 November 2018.

	hand and, where present, from the left hand.	impossible. If the fingerprinting of fewer than 10 fingers is possible, the maximum number of fingerprints shall be taken.
EES	Facial image and data relating to the four fingerprints of the index, middle finger, ring finger and little finger from the right hand where present, and otherwise from the left hand.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Children under the age of 12 shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints. • Persons for whom fingerprinting is physically impossible shall be exempt from the requirement to give fingerprints.
Eurodac	<p>Data relating to fingerprints of all or at least the index fingers, and if those are missing, the prints of all other fingers of a person, or a latent fingerprint.</p> <p>The recently amended Eurodac proposal released in September 2020 proposes to add the facial image⁶².</p>	<p>Each Member State shall promptly take the fingerprints of all fingers of every third-country national or stateless person of at least 14 years of age who is apprehended by the competent control authorities in connection with the irregular crossing.</p> <p>Where it is not possible to take the fingerprints of the apprehended person on account of measures taken to ensure his or her health or the protection of public health, the Member State concerned shall take and send such fingerprints as soon as possible and no later than 48 hours after those health grounds no longer prevail.</p> <p>The recently amended Eurodac proposal released in September 2020 proposes to lower the age for</p>

⁶² Amended proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the establishment of 'Eurodac' for the comparison of biometric data for the effective application of Regulation (EU) XXX/XXX [Regulation on Asylum and Migration Management] and of Regulation (EU) XXX/XXX [Resettlement Regulation], for identifying an illegally staying third-country national or stateless person and on requests for the comparison with Eurodac data by Member States' law enforcement authorities and Europol for law enforcement purposes and amending Regulations (EU) 2018/1240 and (EU) 2019/818.

		biometric data collection from 14 to 6 years old ⁶³ .
ECRIS-TCN	Facial image and the data relating to plain and rolled impressions of the fingerprints of each of a person's fingers.	N/A
ETIAS	No biometrics	N/A

These six systems have key similarities in common; namely, that they primarily—but not exclusively—relate to third-country nationals and that most of them collect biometric data⁶⁴.

As established in the figure 14 below, some of them were created for border management purposes, whereas others were originally built for security purposes.

Figure 3 - Main purposes of the six IT large-scale systems

For border and law enforcement authorities, one of the problems of having numerous information systems is that end-users have to visit so many databases from which they will receive overlapping and delayed information⁶⁵. Therefore, the Interoperability Regulations⁶⁶ were adopted in order to (a) increase the effectiveness of border checks, (b) help to prevent and combat irregular migration, (c) reinforce the level of security within the EU, (d) promote the implementation of the common visa

⁶³ Ibidem.

⁶⁴ C. Blasi Casagran, Fundamental Rights Implications of Interconnecting Migration and Policing Databases in the EU, *Human Rights Law Review*, 2021, p.2.

⁶⁵ Ibid., p.5.

⁶⁶ Regulation (EU) 2019/817 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2019 on establishing a framework for interoperability between EU information systems in the field of borders and visa and amending Regulations (EC) No 767/2008, (EU) 2016/399, (EU) 2017/2226, (EU) 2018/1240, (EU) 2018/1726 and (EU) 2018/1861 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Decisions 2004/512/EC and 2008/633/JHA and Regulation (EU) 2019/818 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2019 on establishing a framework for interoperability between EU information systems in the field of police and judicial cooperation, asylum and migration and amending Regulations (EU) 2018/1726, (EU) 2018/1862 and (EU) 2019/816.

policy, (e) detect, prevent and investigate terrorist and other serious crimes and (f) help identify unknown and undocumented persons.

To achieve these objectives, the six above-mentioned large-scale databases are merged and crosschecked through four new components: The European Search Portal (ESP), the shared Biometric Matching Service (BMS), the Common Identity Repository (CIR) and the Multiple-Identity Detector (MID).

Each of these four interoperability components has been created for a specific purpose:

- The ESP will enable the searching of alphanumeric or biometric data through the six databases, plus Interpol and Europol data;
- The shared BMS will extract biometric ‘templates’ from each of the six EU databases with the purpose of facilitating the searching and cross-matching of the biometric data;
- The CIR will store the biometric and biographic data of non-EU nationals, collected via Eurodac, the VIS, EES, ETIAS and ECRIS-TCN;
- The MID will make “identity confirmation files” whenever a new file is created or updated in the EES, VIS or ETIAS, and an alert on a person is created or updated in the SIS, or a new record is created or modified in the ECRIS-TCN. The MID will store links between the individuals present in more than one of these systems, and these links will be labelled in four categories: white, yellow, green and red.

4.1.2.2 Impacts of large-scale IT systems on human rights

The EU large-scale IT systems as merged by the Interoperability Regulations may have negative implications on different human rights.

1. **Data protection and privacy:** One of the central fundamental rights questions of the Interoperability Regulations relates to the principle of purpose limitation. The regulations blur partly the boundaries between migration management and the fight against (serious) crime and terrorism⁶⁷. “Differences based on national origin are in essence the purpose for adopting the Interoperability regulations, as they incorporate additional security checks for third-country nationals, allowing a differentiated treatment between EU citizens and third-country nationals. The new Regulations place in the same box short-stay travellers, migrants, asylum seekers, irregular migrants and criminals, having only one thing in common: they are third-country nationals. No connection whatsoever to an illegal behaviour will be considered when collecting their data. Thus, this system seems to be based on the (wrong) idea that non-EU nationals are more likely than EU nationals to be engaged in activities threatening public,

⁶⁷ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, “Interoperability and fundamental rights implications”, FRA Opinion – 1/2018, p.10.

bringing closer the controversial concept of ‘pre-crime’. It certainly creates an unjustified difference of treatment between EU citizens and third-country nationals”⁶⁸.

2. **Equality before the law and non-discrimination:** “Interoperability can lead to differentiated treatment of people based on their sex, race, colour, disability or other grounds prohibited by the non-discrimination clause in Article 21 of the Charter. [...] The risk of discrimination is highest with the Multiple Identity Detector, which needs to be carefully assessed from different perspectives. The first one relates to sex. Women more frequently change their last name than men. In many countries, when a woman marries she takes on the family name of her husband. A woman who is in an IT system with her premarriage name and travels again will feature as a person having two different identities. The impact of the change of surname will depend on how sophisticated the algorithm for the automatic verification of multiple identity is. Nevertheless, statistically, women will remain more likely to be stopped at first entry compared to men (for example, where in addition to their surname other pieces of information such as passport details following a renewal of the document do not match) with the risk of missing connecting flights or other important commitments. This risk is higher where biometrics are not used, as is the case in ETIAS and partly in SIS, as searchable biometrics are only now gradually being introduced in SIS. Also other groups of individuals – for example people from societies where certain names are very frequent (e.g. Mr/Ms Lee; Mohammed; etc.) – are likely to face more problems than others when their identities are verified. [...] Persons who as a reflection of their social origin make mistakes when they complete an ETIAS request from their homes are one category who is likely to face more problems. [...] The risk of unfavourable treatment may also originate from an unreliable biometric match. In case of facial recognition, phenotypical origin – thus the colour of the skin – plays also a role, as white skin reflects light more than dark skin and not enough illumination for very dark skin may result in false match”⁶⁹.
3. **Special attention for certain categories of people:** “Next to non-discrimination, interoperability may bring unforeseen negative consequences for children, older persons and persons with disabilities. Persons with disabilities enjoy the “freedom to seek, receive and impart information and ideas on an equal basis with others and through all forms of communication of their choice”, in line with Article 21 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. The fact that they are not able to provide fingerprints making thus a comparison based on biometrics not possible, should not result in disadvantageous treatment. The reliability of a fingerprint (but also a facial image) match decreases when fingerprints taken at a young age are compared many years after the time they were collected. With age fingertips also deteriorate which may affect the reliability of a match”⁷⁰.

⁶⁸ C. Blasi Casagran, op.cit, p.21.

⁶⁹ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, “Interoperability and fundamental rights implications”, op. cit., pp. 13-14.

⁷⁰ Ibid., p.14.

4. **Impacts on other human rights:** Negative consequences on other human rights might derive from “mistakes in the system and in the automated processing of personal data can have on an individual. For example, when the system fails to recognize an individual or if the extension of a visa is not included in the database, a person might be denied entry into an EU Member State or, in the worst case, run the risk of being apprehended and detained. The person affected may face difficulties to prove that he/she really is the person he/she claims to be. In the case of third-country nationals travelling to the EU, this vulnerability might be compounded by language problems. Many problems could occur, for example data errors, but also fraud and forgery of biometric data and incorrect or not up to date personal data included in the IT system. The most likely implication of incorrect data in the Entry Exit system concern the risks of persons mistakenly flagged as over-stayers and the use that police, immigration or other officials may make of such information”⁷¹. A last non-negligible negative consequence is, when applicable, the relative difficulty to exercise the rights to access, rectification or erasure of personal data being processed in EU-large scale databases.

4.1.2.3 *Dealing with the impact of the use of large-scale IT systems within METICOS*

Within METICOS, in order to reflect the human rights’ concerns deriving from the use of large-scale IT systems, it is recommended to:

- Involve participants of which personal data is being processed by the different EU-large scale databases listed in table 13. This might be achieved by involving the target groups identified in table 7 of this Deliverable.
- Involve participants of different:
 - a) age-groups, including elderly (children will not be involved in the pilots but a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns, for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders – see section 6);
 - b) language;
 - c) gender;
 - d) race /ethnicity;
 - e) Nationality;
 - f) religious philosophical beliefs;
 - g) health condition, in particular disabilities;
 - h) Sexual orientation.

This might be achieved by involving the target groups being identified in table 8 of this Deliverable.

⁷¹ European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights, “FRA survey in the framework of the eu-LISA pilot on smart borders – travellers’ views on and experiences of smart borders”, in Smart Borders Pilot Project Technical Report Annexes, Volume 2, 2015, p. 308.

- In the questionnaires being circulated (as well as in the questions asked via the METICOS mobile and tablet applications), it is recommended to include questions such as:
 - Do you believe that the processing of biometric data in EU large-scale databases is humiliating (intrusive to your dignity)?
 - Do you believe that the processing of biometric data in EU large-scale databases is intrusive to your privacy?
 - Do you believe it is important to be informed on why biometric identifiers are processed in several EU large-scale databases?
 - Do you consider that the processing of the facial image in EU large-scale databases is important to secure borders?
 - Do you consider that the processing of fingerprints in EU large-scale databases is important to secure borders?
 - How comfortable do you feel with facial image being processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - How comfortable do you feel with fingerprints being processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Which biometrics are you more in favour of to be processed in EU large scale databases (facial image or fingerprints)?
 - Would you prefer EU large-scale databases not to contain any biometrics?
 - Do you trust the accuracy and reliability of the information (both alphanumerical and biometric) processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Do you believe that personal data are securely stored in EU large scale databases?
 - Would you have problems with the police accessing your biometric data in Eu large scale databases ?
 - Do you believe that the processing of information (both alphanumerical and biometric) is discriminatory on grounds of sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation?
 - Under what age do you consider that fingerprints should not be processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Under what age do you consider that facial image should not be processed in EU large-scale databases?
 - Do you believe that personal data processed in EU large scale databases can be easily corrected in case of mistakes?
 - Do you believe that automated systems would cause more or less discrimination compared to checks done by border guards?

The aim of this recommendation is not to provide a final list of questions to be included in the questionnaires. This draft list is only a recommendation for WP5 partners.

4.2 Evaluation of impacts on human rights deriving from the METICOS platform

This section analyses the impacts on human rights of the data processing operations that are/were envisaged to be conducted by the METICOS platform in order to measure the users' acceptance and the efficiency of border control technologies.

4.2.1 Impact of Facial Emotion Recognition

During early discussions within the METICOS consortium, it was considered to use cameras with facial emotion recognition as a primary data source for the METICOS platform. The aim was to use such technology to analyze facial expressions of travellers (and participants during the pilots) in order to measure their acceptance of border control technologies. After ethical examination, this option was discarded for the reasons mentioned in this sub-section.

4.2.1.1 Risks of using facial emotion recognition

The EDPS defines “Facial Emotion Recognition” (hereafter “FER”) as being “a technology used for analysing sentiments by different sources, such as pictures and videos. It belongs to the family of technologies often referred to as “affective computing”, a multidisciplinary field of research on computer’s capabilities to recognise and interpret human emotions and affective states and it often builds on Artificial Intelligence technologies”⁷².

The supervisory body considers that the complexity of facial expressions, the potential use of the technology in any context, and the involvement of new technologies such as artificial intelligence raise significant privacy and data protection risks:

- A first risk is non-proportionality: “Turning human expressions into a data source to infer emotions clearly touches a part of peoples’ most private data. Being a disruptive technology, FER raises important issues regarding necessity and proportionality. It has to be carefully assessed, whether deploying FER is indeed necessary for achieving the pursued objectives or whether there is a less intrusive alternative”⁷³.
- A second risk is the lack of data accuracy: “Analysis of emotions based on facial expressions may not be accurate, as facial expressions can slightly vary among individuals, may mix different emotional states experienced at the same time (e.g. fear and anger, happy and sad) or may not express an emotion at all. On the other hand, there are emotions that may not be expressed on someone’s face, thus inference based solely on facial expression may lead to wrong impressions. Additional factors can add to the ambiguity of the facial expressions, such as contextual clauses (sarcasm), and socio-cultural context. In addition, technical aspects (different angles of the camera, lighting conditions and masking several parts of the face) can affect the quality of a captured facial expression. Furthermore, even in the case of accurate recognition of emotions, the use of the results may lead to wrong inferences about a person, as FER does not explain the trigger of emotions, which may be a thought of a recent or past event”⁷⁴.

⁷²EDPS, TechDispatch #1/2021 - Facial Emotion Recognition, May 2021, available at https://edps.europa.eu/data-protection/our-work/publications/techdispatch/techdispatch-12021-facial-emotion-recognition_en

⁷³ Ibidem.

⁷⁴ Ibidem.

- A third risk is a lack of fairness: “The accuracy of the facial emotion algorithm results can play an important role in discriminating on grounds of skin colour or ethnic origin. Societal norms and cultural differences have been found to influence the level of expression of some emotions while some algorithms have been found to be biased against several groups, based on skin colour. For instance, a study testing algorithms of facial emotion recognition revealed they assigned more negative emotions (anger) to faces of persons of African descent than to other faces. Furthermore, whenever there was ambiguity, the former were scored as angrier”⁷⁵.
- A fourth risk is a lack of transparency and control: “Where the data subjects’ facial expressions are captured in a remote manner, it may not be clear to them which system or application will process their data, for which purposes, and who the controllers are. As a result, they would not be in the position to freely give consent or exercise control over the processing of their personal data, including sharing with third-parties. Where data subjects are not provided with accurate information, access and control over the use of FER, they are deprived of their freedom to select which aspects of their life can be used to affect other contexts (e.g. emotions in social interactions could be used in the context of recruitment). [...] Another consequence of the remote capture of facial expressions and the obscurity of their processing is that data subjects might not be provided with information on which other sources of data these will be aggregated to. Also, advanced AI algorithms add to the complexity of transparency needs, as they may detect slight movements of facial muscle that are unconscious even for the individuals. This would contribute to the unpleasant feeling of vulnerability due to unwanted exposure”⁷⁶.
- A fifth risk is related to the processing of special categories of personal data: “FER technology can detect the existence, changes or total lack of facial expressions, and link this to an emotional state. As a result, in some contexts, algorithms may infer special categories of personal data, such as political opinions or health data. [...] Also, by the lack of facial expressions, algorithms are able to detect signs of alexithymia, a state in which one cannot understand the feelings they experience or lack the words to describe these feelings. This finding can be linked to severe psychiatric and neurological disorders, such as psychosis. Furthermore, analysis of historical data on one’s emotional state may reveal other health conditions such as depression”⁷⁷.
- The last identified risk is related to profiling and automated decision-making: “FER technology could be used for purposes of safeguarding public security, for instance at concerts, sport events or airports, to quickly identify signs of aggression and stress and identify potential terrorists. However, if such an identification was based solely on FER and was not combined with other actions or triggers that this person is dangerous, this could introduce further risks for the data subjects. For instance, a person could be subject to unjustified delays to perform

⁷⁵ Ibidem.

⁷⁶ Ibidem.

⁷⁷ Ibidem.

further security checks or investigations, causing them to miss participation in an event, boarding on a flight or even lead to unjustified arrest”⁷⁸.

4.2.1.2 Dealing with the impact of Facial Emotion Recognition within METICOS

Within METICOS, in order to reflect the human rights’ concerns deriving from the use of facial emotion recognition, it is recommended to:

- Not to use to use cameras with facial emotion recognition as a primary data source for the METICOS platform. At this stage of the project, it is considered that the use of cameras for behavior & emotion detection could potentially lead to a “function creep”. This means that such data might have been used by border control authorities beyond the limits of the research purposes in order to support measures or decisions taken with regard to travelers (profiling/risk management/etc.). As a reminder, the purpose of the METICOS platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions. The use of facial emotion recognition cameras could have led to the processing of data beyond the scope of the project by providing end-users with data permitting individual (and real-time) decisions that could provoke negative consequences for travelers (for example, further security checks without legal justification in the Border Schengen Code).
- As an alternative to the use of FER, to analyze further the possibility and relevance of collecting data via “traditional” cameras (or physical presence of researchers) on the basis of the informed consent of pilot participants. Such an additional source of data might provide interesting information about the concrete interaction of travellers with border control technologies.

4.2.2 Impact of collecting data from official border control databases and travel documents

As reminded in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”, article 5, §1, c) of the General Data Protection Regulation imposes personal data to be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed”.

The principle of “data minimization” means that a data controller should limit the collection of personal information to what is directly relevant and necessary to accomplish a specified purpose. In other words, data controllers should collect only the personal data they really need to pursue their aim.

In the context of METICOS, the purpose of the platform is to explore both travelers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes toward border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision

⁷⁸ Ibidem.

makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions. Given this specified purpose, it was decided:

- Not to collect data from travel documents. It was considered that it is not necessary for the purposes of the METICOS project to collect information enabling the individualization of each traveler/border control staff member (first name, last name, date of birth, etc.). Indeed, for the purposes of the project, it is only necessary to collect some generic demographic data (Nationality, Gender, Age/Age group, Frequent Flyer, Travel Habits/Experience, Level of Education, Sex, Familiarity with Technology/ Technology Awareness, Cultural Background/Orientation, Trust in BC Authorities, Need for special attention/assistance, country of birth, Residence + Current occupation, Current work status [employed-unemployed-self-employed], per traveler or Rank, Work Experience, per staff member). Such demographic data is collected via the METICOS Mobile Application, the METICOS Tablet Application and Questionnaires. This alternative also offers more transparency during the data collection.
- Not to collect personal data from Border Control Databases such as VIS, SIS, EES, ETIAS, etc. It was considered that such extremely sensitive data were absolutely not needed for the purposes of the project.
- Not to collect data from biometric sensors (e-gates, scanners, etc.) at border crossing points. It was considered that such data collection is not needed for the purposes of the project. Instead, it was decided that obtaining statistics about their use was sufficient (Number of access attempts with documents not accepted by the system; Number of access attempts with non-eligible documents; Number of complaints regarding SBC technologies (by date); Downtime of system per month/year; False Accept Rate / False Reject Rate; Total verification time; Total access time; Total time of biometric and document verification).

As regards the last point, this is also in line with FRONTEX' recommendations related to quality assurance of ABC systems, according to which "for statistical purposes, it is RECOMMENDED to use a minimum amount of anonymised data, such as nationality of the traveller, for each transaction. Storage of personal data identifying the traveller, including the passport number, SHOULD be avoided without proper justification"⁷⁹. Another document of FRONTEX lists the minimum recommended anonymous operational data to be collected for quality assurance and for the extraction of business statistics in ABC systems⁸⁰.

An overview of the planned anonymized statistics that the METICOS consortium envisages to collect from end-users organizations (MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS, CYPOL) is provided in D3.1 – "Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)". Once the availability of the end-users' data will be confirmed and in order to ensure that the anonymization processes will be carried out effectively by

⁷⁹ FRONTEX, Best Practice Operational Guidelines for Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems, 2015, p.53.

⁸⁰ See section 6 of FRONTEX, Best Practice Technical Guidelines for Automated Border Control (ABC) Systems, 2015.

the end-user organizations before that the information is transmitted to the METICOS platform, it is planned to organize a workshop with MoCP/EDPD, ITPFT, ASBGS and CYPOL. This workshop will be dedicated to discussing the anonymization techniques being applied in order to avoid risks of re-identification. These anonymization techniques will be detailed in D3.6 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)”, due on M32.

4.2.3 Management of AI biases

Following the EC’s ethical review that was held between 16/09/201 and 29/10/2021, the following comment was made: *“The beneficiary must submit as a deliverable a report providing an ethical analysis of the AI systems developed or incorporated into the project technologies and the corresponding mitigation actions to address the ethics issues”*⁸¹. In addition, several recommendations were made to address Artificial Intelligence biases in the following tasks: T3.3, T3.5, T4.1, T4.3, T4.5, T5.4, T6.2, T6.3, T7.1, T7.2, T7.3, T7.4, T8.1, T8.2, T8.3, T9.1, T10.3, T10.4, T11.1.

For that reason, and although the METICOS platform does not qualify as “high-risk AI system” in the sense of article 6(2) and Annex III of the proposal AI Act⁸², this section aims to identify and mitigate the potential biases that may occur in the different components of the METICOS platform.

For the purposes of this section:

- Artificial Intelligence systems are defined as follows: *“software (and possibly also hardware) systems designed by humans that, given a complex goal, act in the physical or digital dimension by perceiving their environment through data acquisition, interpreting the collected structured or unstructured data, reasoning on the knowledge, or processing the information, derived from this data and deciding the best action(s) to take to achieve the given goal. AI systems can either use symbolic rules or learn a numeric model, and they can also adapt their behaviour by analysing how the environment is affected by their previous actions”*⁸³.
- Bias is defined as follows *“Bias is an inclination of prejudice towards or against a person, object, or position. Bias can arise in many ways in AI systems. For example, in data-drive AI*

⁸¹ METICOS EC’s Ethical review, p.12.

⁸² Indeed, the METICOS platform cannot be considered as one of the following systems: Migration, asylum and border control management: (a)AI systems intended to be used by competent public authorities as polygraphs and similar tools or to detect the emotional state of a natural person; (b)AI systems intended to be used by competent public authorities to assess a risk, including a security risk, a risk of irregular immigration, or a health risk, posed by a natural person who intends to enter or has entered into the territory of a Member State; (c)AI systems intended to be used by competent public authorities for the verification of the authenticity of travel documents and supporting documentation of natural persons and detect non-authentic documents by checking their security features; (d)AI systems intended to assist competent public authorities for the examination of applications for asylum, visa and residence permits and associated complaints with regard to the eligibility of the natural persons applying for a status. See Annex III, point 7 of the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain union legislative acts, Com/2021/206 Final.

⁸³ Independent high-level expert group on Artificial Intelligence set up by the European Commission, Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, April 2019, p.36.

systems, such as those produced through machine learning, bias in data collection and training can result in an AI system demonstrating bias. In logic-based AI, such as rule-based systems, bias can arise due to how a knowledge engineer might view the rules that apply in a particular setting. Bias can also arise due to online learning and adaptation through interaction. It can also arise through personalisation whereby users are presented with recommendations or information feeds that are tailored to the user's tastes. It does not necessarily relate to human bias or human-driven data collection. It can arise, for example, through the limited contexts in which a system is used, in which case there is no opportunity to generalise it to other contexts. Bias can be good or bad, intentional or unintentional. In certain cases, bias can result in discriminatory and/or unfair outcomes”⁸⁴.

In order to identify the potential biases that may arise in any phase of the development of the METICOS components, we used the NIST Special Publication 1270 – “Towards a Standard for Identifying and Managing Bias in Artificial Intelligence”⁸⁵. Amongst others, this document contains a very comprehensive terminology to classify the different types of biases.

As for the mitigation measures that might be used to manage the identified biases, the following requirements listed in the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI⁸⁶ were taken into account:

1. **Human agency and oversight:** AI systems should empower human beings, allowing them to make informed decisions and fostering their fundamental rights. At the same time, proper oversight mechanisms need to be ensured, which can be achieved through human-in-the-loop, human-on-the-loop, and human-in-command approaches
2. **Technical Robustness and safety:** AI systems need to be resilient and secure. They need to be safe, ensuring a fall-back plan in case something goes wrong, as well as being accurate, reliable and reproducible. That is the only way to ensure that also unintentional harm can be minimized and prevented.
3. **Privacy and data governance:** besides ensuring full respect for privacy and data protection, adequate data governance mechanisms must also be ensured, taking into account the quality and integrity of the data, and ensuring legitimised access to data.
4. **Transparency:** the data, system and AI business models should be transparent. Traceability mechanisms can help achieving this. Moreover, AI systems and their decisions should be explained in a manner adapted to the stakeholder concerned. Humans need to be aware that they are interacting with an AI system and must be informed of the system's capabilities and limitations.
5. **Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness:** Unfair bias must be avoided, as it could have multiple negative implications, from the marginalization of vulnerable groups, to the exacerbation of prejudice and discrimination. Fostering diversity, AI systems should be

⁸⁴ Ibidem.

⁸⁵ This publication is available free of charge from <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1270>.

⁸⁶ Independent high-level expert group on Artificial Intelligence set up by the European Commission, Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI, April 2019.

accessible to all, regardless of any disability, and involve relevant stakeholders throughout their entire life circle.

6. **Societal and environmental well-being:** AI systems should benefit all human beings, including future generations. It must hence be ensured that they are sustainable and environmentally friendly. Moreover, they should take into account the environment, including other living beings, and their social and societal impact should be carefully considered.

On the basis of this methodology to identify the potential biases and the applicable mitigation measures, table 14 was circulated to the technical partners developing the METICOS components and technologies.

In Table 14 below, the rows are filled as follows:

- Row 1: identifies the Task Leader responsible for the technology or component.
- Row 2: summarizes the recommendations of the European Commission (from the Ethical review).
- Row 3: describes the Task Leader plans to address the EC's ethical recommendations.
- Row 4: Based on the NIST' bias terminology, this row identifies the potential bias at the pre-design stage and describes how the Task Leader envisages to mitigate each identified bias.
- Row 5: Based on the NIST' bias terminology, this row identifies the potential bias at the design and development phase and describes how the Task Leader envisages to mitigate each identified bias.
- Row 6: Based on the NIST' bias terminology, this row identifies the potential bias at the deployment stage and describe how the Task Leader envisage to mitigate each identified bias.

Table 14 - Identification and mitigation of biases

Task & Leader	EC's recommendation	Action proposed by Task Leader	Identification and mitigation of bias at pre-design stage	Identification and mitigation of bias at design and development stage	Identification and mitigation of bias at deployment stage
T3.5 (EDPD)	(Stakeholder-sensitive recommendations on coping with security-related perceptions of the EU): should be expanded to consider the dangers of bias and discrimination in AI systems, or their use thereof. Recommendations should detail mechanisms by which end-users and policy makers should be made aware of these dangers and the limitations they impose upon	<p>1. Development and application of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) at EU level, so as the end users of the METICOS technologies to have a common approach and share the same views, values and perspectives regarding the management of personal data. Furthermore the SOPs shall be updated frequently with new procedures as a paradigm shift is highly likely to take place.</p> <p>2. Implementation of training activities for the end users at EU level, via webinars, with</p>	<p>Cognitive bias: Redesign of the questionnaire.</p> <p>Content production bias: Evaluation of the feedback received and the structure of the questionnaire. Request for additional clarifications by the target group and redesign of the questionnaire.</p> <p>Activity bias: Resend of the questionnaire in case that the number of responses is unsatisfactory.</p> <p>Data generation bias: Evaluation of the data received from the target group so as to determine their quality and redundancy. Request for additional</p>	<p>N/A: As task leaders of T3.5, our contribution ends at the pre-design stage, by gathering all the data required so as the other technical partners to proceed with the design and development of the AI technologies. However, we mention below some types of biases that could possibly be elaborated further by the technical partners.</p> <p>Cognitive bias</p> <p>Human Reporting bias</p> <p>Concept Drift bias</p> <p>Consumer bias</p> <p>Mode confusion bias</p> <p>Population bias</p>	<p>N/A: As task leaders of T3.5, our contribution ends at the pre-design stage, by gathering all the data required so as the other technical partners to proceed with the design and development of the AI technologies. However, we mention below some types of biases that could possibly be elaborated further by the technical partners.</p> <p>Cognitive bias</p> <p>Automation complacency bias</p> <p>Behavioral bias</p> <p>Concept drift bias</p> <p>Mode confusion bias</p>

	<p>expectations of AI trustworthiness.</p>	<p>the potential involvement of CEPOL.</p> <p>3. Close monitoring of the bias cases. In our point of view, this is twofold. Both an end user and the AI can be biased. The first case is mitigated by training and education while the other requires redesign of the AI and the potential use of synthetic data. In this case it is important to use unbiased data, since an AI technology is as good as the data that it gets.</p> <p>4. Monitoring and evaluation of the behavioral activity of the end users. Recording and storage of every action performed by the</p>	<p>feedback in case of poor results.</p> <p>Population bias: Expansion of the target group to other countries and entities involved in the border management. Redesign of the questionnaire so as to include information about demographics and education level of the</p> <p>Selective adherence: Evaluation of the feedback received from more than one employee.</p> <p>Societal bias: Development of a neutral questionnaire so as to avoid any personal judgement on social groups, thus resulting into poor quality feedback.</p>	<p>Data generation bias</p> <p>Presentation bias</p> <p>Selective adherence</p> <p>Systemic bias</p> <p>Societal bias</p>	<p>Presentation bias</p> <p>Deployment bias</p> <p>Selective adherence</p> <p>Systemic bias</p> <p>Loss of situational awareness bias</p> <p>Exclusion bias</p>
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		<p>users, frequent audits on an annual sample and development of additional AI technology by which the AI can understand and report any cases of corruption and inappropriate behavior of the end users.</p> <p>5. Finally in the context of Task 3.5, the qualitative data acquired by the questionnaire shall be thoroughly evaluated, from an ethical point of view. If the questionnaire cannot produce tangible results and taken into consideration the fact that we cannot change the target group, then the questionnaire must be redrafted.</p>			
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<p>T4.1 (SIMAVI)</p>	<p>Formal mechanisms to assess influence of bias or discrimination in T4.1 should be implemented. These should be detailed in the relevant deliverable.</p>	<p>In the process of defining the requirements at platform and component level, there was ongoing coordination with the technical partners developing the components. One of the issues that was followed is the prevention of bias and discrimination in the technical components. Each tool owner describes their approach in the deliverables corresponding to their tools.</p>	<p>At predesign phase the available data for the METICOS system was not clear. However, the following general directions were identified for the platform level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • human agency and oversight – this guides what information is presented in the dashboards in order to allow the users to make informed decisions and to ensure human in the loop approach • privacy and data governance – the data kept in the platform does not contain PII, access to data is protected through authentication and 	<p>During the design and development phase work has continued following the 2 directions mentioned. The set of graphs presented in the dashboards was defined so that the user can see relevant statistics based on data that could show bias (statistics about demographics, gender, age, education etc).</p>	<p>Synthetic data will be prepared in order to be used by the METICOS components. This data will be analyzed in order to make sure it will not present bias and discrimination.</p>
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			authorization mechanisms		
T4.3 (SIMAVI)	<p>The architectural definitions should include provision for auditing of data sources and processing by humans. It is stated in 883075--SEALED-PROPOSAL</p> <p>“Partner 1 will lead the architecture definition process, whereas involved partners will contribute to the exploration of the technologies potentially relevant to the areas addressed by the project (e.g. source reliability estimation, cross-sectional signal</p>	<p>In developing the architecture, there was collaboration between the technical partners. The topic of data sources was discussed because the available data didn't cover all the expected information of the tools. The bias of the data and how to deal with was discussed by each tool owner in their deliverables (D5.4, D6.2, D7.5, D7.6)</p>	<p>The main problem that was identified was the lack of enough data (training data bias in NIST terminology). In order to mitigate this, multiple discussion were organized in order to try to identify other relevant data sources.</p>	<p>The main problem that was identified was the lack of enough data (training data bias in NIST terminology). In order to mitigate this, multiple discussion were organized in order to try to identify other relevant data sources.</p>	<p>In order to solve the problem of data availability, the technical partners will prepare synthetic data that will be relevant for the use cases implemented by the tools</p>

	<p>generation, Big Data mining technologies, correlation analysis, etc.) as well as for the identification of the detailed system views, i.e. conceptual, functional, communication, deployment, interfaces etc” (p.49). The range of factors addressed should be expanded to include mechanisms for formal ethical assessment of bias in selection of data sources, bias within data sources, and bias introduced through modelling</p>				
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	(such as inappropriate optimisation). The possibilities for biased or discriminatory interpretation of system output by end-users should also be considered. These factors should be included in the requirements and guidelines passed to other Work Packages, especially T5.4 (TAM Modelling).				
T4.5 (SIMAVI)	Development of credibility profiles for media sources should include formal mechanisms for ensuring there is no bias in	The social media data is processed in Social Toolkit. The analysis on bias can be found in relevant deliverables like D6.2.	N/A: the data sources and data models come from other tasks.	N/A : the data sources and data models come from other tasks.	N/A: the data sources and data models come from other tasks.

	assessment of credibility. A formal definition of what constitutes “credibility” should be produced.				
T5.4 (AIT)	Target criteria for model assessment should include bias as well as accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, computational complexity	Model performance target criteria will be explicitly defined and agreed upon by WP5 partners and the project coordinator. Particular emphasis will be put on bias mitigation by securing explainability and transparency of candidate models. This will be achieved by a) properly documents the underlying datasets in the respective deliverables (D5.3, D5.6) as well as b) by giving preference to white-box algorithms (linear regression, structural equation modeling, etc.) as	Exclusion bias: deliberate, explicit choice of included and excluded subgroups (e.g. people with disabilities) before survey data collection and modeling Popularity bias: specification of sampling for survey data collection towards ensuring equal representation along critical dimensions such as gender and age.	Evaluation bias: careful splitting between training and test datasets, use of suitable stratification and validation techniques (e.g. k-fold cross-validation). Temporal bias: transnational data collection within the same short time window. Training data bias: careful design and monitoring of (survey-based) data collection, collection of data in eight different countries (traveler study). Population bias: collection of data in eight different	Interpretation bias: user-centered design of user-interfaces METICOS modules that use the TMA, including dedicated testing for signs of interpretation bias exhibited by pilot participants. Concept drift: development of suitable model retraining strategies in T5.5 (including detection of concept drift)

		opposed to black-box algorithms (like gradient boosting or neural networks). In cases where the latter is not feasible, state-of-the art explainable AI methods (SHAP, LIME, etc.) will be utilized.		countries (traveler study), inclusion of cultural background framework in data collection.	
T6.2 (NTNU)	Methods for analysing social data should consider the risks of bias or discrimination at any and all stages of data processing, reporting and use. Mechanisms for detecting and alleviating bias and for preventing discrimination should be detailed in D6.2.	All the possible bias will be identified and mitigated at each stage of the architecture pipeline. We are aware of the fact that Twitter is not representative of the population and this results into a bias while developing the perception extraction module e.g. some user may have politically biased views and opinions. We mitigate this kind of bias by using data from additional sources (such as questionnaires, pilots, operational data from the	1. The choice of keywords to use for searching tweets on Twitter may lead to a bias. Following presents the cases of how different keyword based bias is mitigated: Mitigation: i) We used google trends to expand our list of query keywords for searching on Twitter. We searched for “egates” in the google trends and it gives additional relevant keywords	1. The composition of test and training data samples impacts the results. Mitigation: For our set of experiments, we are trying to handle this bias by working on 1) k-fold cross validation and 2) batching in train/test split while training and evaluating the predictive models involved in different components of the perception extraction pipeline.	1. Performance evaluation metrics bias. Mitigation: Except accuracy, we are also considering precision, recall and sensitivity-based evaluation metrics which reveal performance of predictive models on each individual class labels. Based on these performance metrics, we are planning to optimize our experiments related to perception

		<p>pilots) alongside with Twitter.</p>	<p>representing the border control technologies domain. ii) We use keyword search in the twitter API not only on explicitly defined keywords for the tweets such as hashtags but also in the tweet content (i.e. tweet body/text). iii) As per the case of using same keywords for different domains in the tweets, this bias is automatically resolved because our domain is quite distinct in terms of context.</p> <p>2. Access from the programming language API to the Twitter data through APIs is often limited</p>	<p>2. Individual privacy due to data linkage. despite the public nature of users' posts on social media, there is a potential privacy risk that information collected for an intended purpose may be used to achieve other, potentially malevolent goals and that users could be targeted for persecution for their beliefs and opinions. Mitigation: For the risk of identification, the collected data from social media are anonymized while the data collected still can be used for extracting useful insights without</p>	<p>extraction. Hence, improving the experiments will result in the reduction of this bias in reporting of the predicted results.</p> <p>2. Individual privacy due to data linkage. despite the public nature of users' posts on social media, there is a potential privacy risk that information collected for an intended purpose may be used to achieve other, potentially malevolent goals and that users could be targeted for persecution for their beliefs and opinions Mitigation: For the risk of identification,</p>
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			<p>Mitigation: Right now, we are working on data collection from Twitter, and we resolved this bias by using “Twitter Academic Research API”. The main benefits of this API are: i) It gives access for historical data in the form of full-archive search from the complete twitter database. ii) It supports advanced query parameter language to get more precise results of data collection. iii) It supports advanced query parameter language to get more precise results based on keywords, filters such as dates, language, retweets, etc of data collection.</p>	<p>compromising the individual’s privacy. For the purpose-misuse, the purpose of the analysis has been identified and justified in the project's privacy/data protection impact assessment.</p>	<p>the collected data from social media are anonymized while the data collected still can be used for extracting useful insights without compromising the individuals privacy. For the purpose-misuse, the purpose of the analysis has been identified and justified in the project's privacy/data protection impact assessment.</p>
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			<p>iv) The monthly limit for data collection using this API is 10 million, which leads to a very good amount of data.</p> <p>3. Text pre- processing /cleaning operations may affect the resulting pre-processed text. Mitigation: Performing task specific text pre- processing and cleaning operations.</p> <p>4. Individual privacy due to data linkage. despite the public nature of users' posts on social media, there is a potential privacy risk that information collected for an intended purpose may be used</p>		
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			<p>to achieve other, potentially malevolent goals and that users could be targeted for persecution for their beliefs and opinions. Mitigation: For the risk of identification, the collected data from social media are anonymized while the data collected still can be used for extracting useful insights without compromising the individuals privacy. For the purpose-misuse, the purpose of the analysis has been identified and justified in the project's privacy/data protection impact assessment.</p>		
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<p>T6.3 (NTNU)</p>	<p>This task will simulate people passing border controls. The parameters used for defining agents (such as cultural background, religion, lifestyle) should be evaluated for bias and discrimination. In particular, it is important the simulated agent parameters are not skewed in a manner which disguises bias in processing. This evaluation should be made available to, and reported on, by the Ethics Board.</p>	<p>The developed technology acceptance prediction algorithm performance and evaluation criteria will be defined by the WP6 team. All the possible bias will be identified and mitigated at each stage of the METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit pipeline.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Some of the demographics and profile data attributes are not contributing for predicting technology acceptance. Mitigation: i) to find correlation of each demographic / profile data variable vs the variable of technology acceptance in order to identify the impact of demographics/profile data over technology acceptance. 2. Bias: to identify if any data variable such as age-group is more skewed towards any specific value (i.e. 25-34).Mitigation: i) to perform descriptive data analysis to 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Errors due to the missing values. Mitigation: replacing missing values using mean and mode approaches in a way the data attributes should not be skewed. 2. The imbalance of data samples between different class labels used for prediction. Mitigation: The data imbalance in samples for different class labels while developing predictive models is a very frequent problem which always leads to the bias in training of the models and make the predictive models more aligned towards class labels having 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Performance evaluation metrics bias. Mitigation: Except accuracy, we are also considering precision, recall, or sensitivity-based evaluation metrics which reveal performance of predictive models on each individual class labels. Based on these performance metrics, we are planning to optimize our experiments related to perception extraction. Hence, improving the experiments will result in the reduction of bias related to the trained model in reporting of the predicted results.
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			<p>understand how technology acceptance varies based on different data variables from demographics and profile data of the travellers/border guards.</p> <p>3. Individual privacy due to data linkage, there is a potential privacy risk that information collected for an intended purpose may be used to achieve other, potentially malevolent goals and that users could be targeted for persecution for their beliefs and opinions. Mitigation: For the risk of identification, the collected data are anonymized while</p>	<p>majority of the data samples. There are many under sampling and over sampling techniques like SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique), which helps to avoid this bias while training predictive models.</p> <p>3. Individual privacy due to data linkage, there is a potential privacy risk that information collected for an intended purpose may be used to achieve other, potentially malevolent goals and that users could be targeted for persecution for their beliefs and opinions. Mitigation: For the</p>	<p>2. Individual privacy due to data linkage, there is a potential privacy risk that information collected for an intended purpose may be used to achieve other, potentially malevolent goals and that users could be targeted for persecution for their beliefs and opinions. Mitigation: For the risk of identification, the collected data are anonymized while the data collected still can be used for extracting useful insights without compromising the individuals' privacy. For the purpose-misuse, the purpose of the analysis has been identified and</p>
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			<p>the data collected still can be used for extracting useful insights without compromising the individual’s privacy. For the purpose-misuse, the purpose of the analysis has been identified and justified in the project's privacy/data protection impact assessment.</p>	<p>risk of identification, the collected data are anonymized while the data collected still can be used for extracting useful insights without compromising the individuals privacy. For the purpose-misuse, the purpose of the analysis has been identified and justified in the project's privacy/data protection impact assessment.</p> <p>4. The disposition to behave somehow. The Social Sensing Toolkit depends on the data available for training on one side. If the data is representative of travellers and border staff, AI and ML will</p>	<p>justified in the project's privacy/data protection impact assessment.</p>
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				<p>not behave somehow. The more the data is representative the more robust the predictions and outputs of AI and ML are. On the other hand, we make sure that categories or data types relating to unpowered groups or minorities are included in the Social Sensing toolkit in order to enable deterministic but not random behaviour of the toolkit. For example, we will extend the gender categories from 'male' and 'female' to 'male' and 'female' and 'other' in order to be able to address and predict the technology acceptance of</p>	
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				<p>categories such as trans-sexual. In case this information is not provided, the social sensing toolkit will not discriminate. If the training data is not high quality, misleading, lacking etc. for a category, this only means that the predictions of that category may not be reliable. However, this does not mean that there will be any discrimination towards that the category. We always need to keep in mind that we are not developing a border crossing technology that will not discriminate but we are measuring the technology acceptance of</p>	
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				<p>different profiles with the social sensing toolkit and the overall METICOS platform. For employment/job category inputs, we provide open text to users. Hence, if they want, sexual workers can provide their employment category in free form text. If we will be able to collect data about this minority group, then AI and ML will be more able to make predictions about this category. Not being able to make precise predictions about a category does not mean that that particular category will be discriminated. On the other hand, the toolkit eventually may make some</p>	
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				<p>inferencing related to some changes in the technology acceptance of travellers particularly and also of border staff. For example, the toolkit may notice time to time for no visible reason there maybe an lower acceptance score for the technology in use. The toolkit can point to this, and this may lead to an investigation related to which categories are changing their acceptance of technology or if such a change maybe related to minority category. However, we have no means to interfere with how the border crossing technology in use may</p>	
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				<p>offer to the minorities in terms of gender issues for example. There maybe some travellers that may want to cover their sentiment while crossing the border. These may prefer only to give the reply/response to the border authorities they want and hide otherwise. Hence, the social sensing toolkit maybe lead towards wrong learning of the situation which can be solved by looking into the error-rate and doing the fine-tuning. However, the travellers will provide nationality as part of their profiles in the toolkit. So, if people belonging to a nationality provide</p>	
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				<p>wrong sentiment, then toolkit will learn the wrong profile, perception matchings. However, the perception is not only composed of sentiment, but also of attributes such as emotion, subjectivity, feedback on aspects of technology and with these additional attributes, we try to increase the toolkit's reliability and lower the effect of the misinformation by the travellers.</p> <p>Besides, no one is discriminated in the social sensing toolkit. We develop the toolkit in such a way that, whenever we are asked for, we will be able to provide an explanation for the possible reasons for the toolkit making</p>	
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				<p>a particular prediction. If wanted, we will be able to provide what profile at a moment lead to what perceptions and hence the connected technology acceptance score. The more quality data we collect for minorities and train and test the toolkit with, the more reliable predictions it will make. Also, we plan to test the toolkit for minority predictions at our coming pilots such that we can direct the data collection in relevant ways. People without ravel documents and people who are stateless are to be handled by the border staff and the border crossing technology. For that reason, if a person is not able to cross the border, then the social sensing toolkit will not make any predictions for those persons. For the case of human trafficking, social</p>	
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				<p>sensing toolkit is not expected to notice this. Since people again may hide their emotions, sentiment etc. Also, METICOS is not a monitoring platform neither the social sensing toolkit is. Also, overall the goal of METICOS is not to provide any service to any traveller. It is about understanding and predicting technology acceptance of travellers besides border staff. Hence there is no reason or a way for it to discriminate, humiliate or bias anyone versus others. However, again due to the amount, quality, representativeness of the data, the predictions may not be reliable. This does not mean that it will bias, discriminate, humiliate anyone or any minority group. However, it may help figure out if there are any dissatisfaction of the technology in use and convey</p>	
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				<p>this dissatisfaction to the relevant stakeholder’s attention. It can help answer questions such as if technology acceptance is low and why? Is there any missing data on for example, trans sexual groups? Could there be human trafficking? E.g. until last week tech acceptance score was lower on the average and it is much higher now. What is happening? Also we think the border staff should be trained on possible biases for awareness of these. Also, we will provide the limitations of the social sensing toolkit related to bias as we also explicitly identify in this document. We also plan to create a list of the biases and the mitigation measures to be distributed during the pilots.</p>	
T7.1	Numerous opportunities exist	To ensure that data collected for METICOS is	To ensure that the data collection process was	In order to minimize bias during the design and	During the pre-design, design, and development stages,

(MAGG)	<p>within this task for bias or discrimination within datasets, their selection, and their use for the development of models. These include, but are not limited to, selection and processing of social media usage, biometrics and criminal records. Biometrics is a particular concern with regard to bias (see: Drozdowski et al., 'Demographic Bias in Biometrics'. IEEE Transactions on Technology and Society 1, no. 2 (2020): 89–103). Formal</p>	<p>unbiased and relevant to the business needs, it is recommended to use data-set fields that are generic yet still appropriate. This aligns with the EC's guidelines and will enable travellers from diverse backgrounds, experiences, and perspectives to provide honest feedback on the acceptance of modern border control systems. Additionally, data protection and privacy measures should be incorporated into the design and development phase, while data collection methods should be transparent and open. To ensure data accuracy, validation processes must be put in place. The data collection approach should be flexible to accommodate changes and must involve thorough documentation,</p>	<p>unbiased during the pre-design stage, it was crucial to establish clear objectives and develop a set of non-leading questions that would be included in the questionnaire to be completed by travelers after passing through the modern border control points. These questions provide anonymized data and are crucial in ensuring that the collected data is unbiased since they do not influence the respondents' answers and allow for objective analysis by the METICOS components. Diversifying data sources was also key to avoiding bias, which was achieved by collaborating with multiple BCP authorities as data providers. All technical partners of METICOS created a list of desired BCP data, which was then sent to each BCP authority partner. In this way, we were able to include</p>	<p>development stages of data collection and description, constant communication among all partners was crucial. After analyzing all provided data samples from the BCP authorities and conducting a pre-processing stage, the data was stored in the METICOS database for use in the project's predictive models. The traveler questionnaire was then implemented to save all responses in the METICOS infrastructure, allowing partners to access this data in real-time or on demand. These processes followed a standardized data collection protocol approach, based on specific templates, to ensure consistent data collection across all individuals and situations, thus minimizing the risk of bias.</p>	<p>most sources of bias have already been identified and mitigated. However, it is important to establish regular monitoring of deployment outcomes and assess the data collection procedures, providing appropriate training and guidance to all involved parties. Additionally, rigorous testing was conducted across diverse populations to identify and correct any biases in the system, ensuring that the data collection process and predictive models accurately predicted traveler behavior and their acceptance of modern border control systems.</p>
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	<p>mechanisms should be instituted to assess for bias or discrimination in all datasets, the selection of datasets, their use in model development, any interventions in model development (e.g.: optimisation strategies) and the accidental development of bias during machine learning. These mechanisms should be human-auditable and detailed in the planned detailed documentation. This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and</p>	<p>organization, and continuous monitoring and evaluation for any signs of bias.</p>	<p>multiple data sources from different countries, achieving a more diverse and comprehensive dataset. This approach allowed us to gain a better understanding of the effectiveness and acceptance of modern border control systems across various regions and identify any potential biases or discrepancies that may have existed within individual datasets.</p>		
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	included in their reports.				
T7.2 (ICCS)	<p>Bias should be formally assessed during the development of data models, especially regarding the use of natural language processing (for justification of this requirement see: Hovy and Prabhumoye. "Five sources of bias in natural language processing." Language and Linguistics Compass 15.8 (2021): e12432). This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and</p>	<p>In METICOS data model, we capture all the attributes that can be used to identify gender, age, ethnicity etc.</p> <p>The development of data models comprises of two complementary approaches:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data-driven approach using Natural Language Processing techniques - Expert-based approach, where the entities, attributes and relationships will be identified, defined and designed by expert 	<p>In the pre-design phase, the complementary approaches are defined in order to mitigate bias.</p>	<p>In the design and development phase, the complementary approaches are implemented in order to mitigate bias. Since we follow an agile methodology, the feedback is incorporated as part of an ongoing process.</p>	<p>Even at a deployment stage, the agile approach is followed. In case any concept, entity, relationship etc. is missing, it can be added at a later stage. Therefore, there is a feedback loop from deployment stage to development, since, as mentioned previously, the agile standardization approach is followed for data model development and deployment.</p>

	included in their reports.	on the security field. Therefore, the complementarity of this approaches enables the mitigation of bias especially in the field of NLP. Moreover, one of the steps of the first approach includes the evaluation of the application of ML algorithms, using data-driven and human-in-the-loop approaches. The data driven approach includes metrics which are widely used to evaluate the robustness and performance of Machine Learning and Data Analytics algorithms, such as coherence score (Rosner, Hinneburg, Röder, Nettling, & Both, 2014). Regarding the human-in-the-loop approach, we have			
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		<p>evaluated the results using input from domain experts.</p> <p>Regarding the expert-based approach, feedback has been requested and gathered from METICOS consortium partners but also from experts from projects in the BES cluster. Furthermore, it is noteworthy to mention that since an agile standardization approach is followed in the definition of METICOS data model, the feedback, as soon as it is gathered, is incorporated in the data model and more phases of refinement follow, in order to derive the final METICOS data model.</p>			
T7.3 (ICCS)	The semantic and sentiment analysis techniques planned can	It is known from the literature that Automatic machine learning systems can inadvertently	Identify ways to mitigate bias: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Multilingual capabilities 	Bias can originate from any or several parts of a system: the labeled and unlabeled datasets used to learn	After implementation, we aim to provide evaluation on the way the bias is handled. This should be an agile iterative

	<p>introduce various biases (see: Thelwall, Mike. "Gender bias in sentiment analysis." (2018), Online Information Review; Kiritchenko and Saif. "Examining gender and race bias in two hundred sentiment analysis systems." (2018) arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.04508). Formal</p>	<p>accentuate and perpetuate inappropriate human biases. That is why we aim to mitigate these biases by the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Including a multitude of languages - Being aware that any sample of textual data may include some sort of bias. Therefore, this data is not sufficient to draw conclusions, that is why it should be complemented by other datasets, such as questionnaire data and operational data which include demographics information. Moreover, as part 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Descriptive data analysis to understand how technology acceptance varies based on different data variables from demographics and profile data of the travellers/border guards. - Thorough planning will be held in advance regarding the participants taking part in the METICOS pilot execution in order to create a representative sample together with the partners responsible for organising the pilot activities. 	<p>different parts of the model, the language resources used (e.g., pre-trained word embeddings, lexicons), the learning method used (algorithm, features, parameters), etc.</p> <p>Since we follow an agile methodology, the feedback from the bias mitigation obtained in the previous step is incorporated as part of an ongoing process in the design and development phase.</p>	<p>process. This is achieved by integrating the bias identification and mitigation pipeline in our analysis.</p>
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		of our pipeline, we have merely used data retrieved from twitter in order to verify the capabilities of our system and framework.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using appropriate bias identification and mitigation tML methods and toolkits (i.e. AIF360 (Bellamy, et al., 2018)) we will expose to the user the cross-tabular analysis per age, gender, etc. based on the available data. 		
T7.4 (ICCS)	Data sources should be evaluated for pre-existing bias or features which should lead to discrimination. For example, any facial recognition systems should be evaluated for gender and racial bias disparities in accuracy. Data mining systems produced in the	<p>Several avenues are going to be pursued to address these inequities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ADME for structured data is a framework, which is able to handle, process and fuse a multitude of data streams including various data assets. This will help decrease the bias introduced by only one data asset. 	<p>Identify ways to mitigate bias:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Plan to include balanced dataset in respect to demographics (age, gender, race) To ensure that, descriptive analytics will be performed before the use of the dataset. - Include in the suite of algorithms in-processing algorithms which 	<p>Implement the identified ways. Some of the biases which are of relevance include representation bias, aggregation bias, algorithmic bias, population bias. Some of the ways to achieve the mitigation of bias include the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fair Machine Learning (pre-, in- and post-processing) - Explainability techniques using 	<p>After implementation, we aim to provide evaluation on the way the bias is handled. This should be an integral part of the component developed to tackle bias or features that lead to discrimination. This should be an agile iterative process. This is achieved by integrating the bias identification and mitigation pipeline in our analysis.</p>

	<p>project should contain mechanisms for bias correction. This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and included in their reports.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analysis can be performed regarding statistics for indicators of acceptance, as well as quantitative statistics which refer to the characteristics of the SBCT (i.e. FAR) in relation to demographics (age, gender, gender group etc.) - Last but not least, analysis will be executed and presented by gender, age and race whenever available. For instance, in the analytics dashboard the user will be able to view results/correlations in their totality or 	<p>have bias correction mechanisms. We have included adversarial debiasing [43]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Incorporate a bias identification and mitigation pipeline within the METICOS component developed as part of T7.5 whose purpose is to identify and correct the introduced bias of the dataset. More information about this component and pipeline can be found as part of Deliverable D7.6. 	<p>LIME and SHAP python tools.</p> <p>Both of the above are implemented as part of bias identification and mitigation pipeline within the METICOS component developed as part of T7.5 whose purpose is to identify and correct the introduced bias of the dataset. More information about this component and pipeline can be found as part of Deliverable D7.6.</p>	
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		filter these by gender/ age/ race/ country.			
T8.1 (MAGG)	Existing datasets should be evaluated for bias. Remediation processes should be incorporated as appropriate. Attention should be given to the potential of middleware and API's to introduce bias. The data flow diagram should include specific components for detection and remediation of bias. The project border policies drawn from Romania should be amended to cater for any identified	To avoid introducing bias through APIs, it's important to take several steps. Firstly, pre-existing datasets should be anonymized and filtered to remove any data that could potentially introduce bias. Secondly, the training data used to develop the API should be diverse and unbiased, and algorithms should be tested for fairness. Additionally, careful consideration should be given to the selection of variables and parameters used in the API, as the inclusion or exclusion of certain variables can affect the potential for bias in the resulting data. Finally, it's important to continuously monitor and	In the pre-design stage of database building and deployment, bias can be introduced in various steps. To avoid such biases, the METICOS team took a number of steps. Firstly, they identified potential sources of bias in the data, followed by the establishment of clear data collection and storage policies. Additionally, to minimize bias, the team ensured diverse representation in their data sources, testing samples, and research methods. This approach helped to ensure that their findings and conclusions were based on a broad range of perspectives and were not unduly	In the process of designing and developing the METICOS databases, potential sources of bias were considered from the pre-design stage. To ensure high data quality and minimize bias, careful evaluation of the data used to fill the databases was conducted. Multiple sources of data were utilized to diversify the data. Data normalization was applied wherever appropriate to eliminate imbalances in the data. Transparency was maintained in all database processes for end-users, and regular reviews and updates were conducted for both the databases and their processes.	After the deployment of the METICOS databases, an assessment was conducted to evaluate the presence of bias. This involved a thorough examination of the algorithms and data used, as well as testing and validation to ensure their correct functioning. To ensure ongoing accuracy and impartiality, regular monitoring of the databases is carried out, with close examination of data usage patterns and user feedback to identify potential sources of bias and make necessary adjustments. These monitoring activities are an integral part of the METICOS team's ongoing commitment to ensuring that their system

	issues of bias, and to reflect the appropriate levels of trustworthiness of these potentially biased systems. This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and included in their reports.	evaluate the API's performance and adjust it as needed to minimize any potential biases.	influenced by any particular group or individual.		is both effective and unbiased.
T8.2 (MAGG)	Data structures developed under this task should be evaluated for bias once completed. Virtualisation layers and any other elements created which aggregate and/or abstract lower-tier data should be evaluated for bias. The middleware security and	To develop a platform for orchestrating heterogeneous data sources and intelligence, such as the METICOS Middleware, it is crucial to assess the data sources in advance to identify potential sources of bias. Anonymization of the data is essential to prevent the possibility of identifying individuals based on the data collected. It is also important to ensure that	In the pre-design stage, the METICOS Middleware took steps to prevent bias in data collection and management. To achieve this, the Middleware developed data structures that are as generic as possible while still providing relevant information to train AI models in other components. The Middleware's APIs effectively manage all available data sources (BCP data, external sources,	The METICOS Middleware platform has undergone a thorough assessment to ensure that bias is minimized in all layers. To prevent any potential biases from being introduced, the data passing through the platform and being stored in the databases is not aggregated in a way that could produce bias. Additionally, the data is anonymized and sourced from diverse stakeholders. To maintain high data quality,	To prevent bias in the METICOS middleware APIs after deployment, ongoing monitoring and evaluation of its performance are crucial. This includes analyzing the API results and comparing them to known ground truth data to identify any potential biases. It's also important to regularly update and review the training data used to develop the API by incorporating new and diverse data sources and

	<p>privacy module should be expanded to include appropriate mechanisms for prevention of biased or discriminatory usage. This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and included in their reports.</p>	<p>the data is diverse and inclusive, representing a broad range of perspectives. Thorough documentation of the process is essential to identify and address any instances of bias in a consistent and transparent manner. To ensure ongoing fairness and accuracy, continuous monitoring and evaluation of the platform for potential sources of bias are also essential. By following these steps, the METICOS team has been able to develop a platform that is robust, effective, and provides valuable insights into the behavior of travelers at modern border control points.</p>	<p>questionnaires etc.) by using variables to parameterize queries and avoid partiality towards specific data sources. All data stored on the platform is anonymized and filtered to remove irrelevant or duplicate entries, and the storing processes are well-defined and documented to ensure consistent and reliable data storage.</p>	<p>regular reviews are conducted to identify missing data, errors, or biases. The platform is also closely monitored and audited on a frequent basis to ensure transparency and accountability in all data-related processes.</p>	<p>ensuring the data is representative of the population to which the API will be applied. Additionally, testing the API for fairness across different groups and characteristics, such as gender, race, and age, is necessary to prevent any unfair favoring or discrimination.</p>
<p>T8.3 (NET-U)</p>	<p>“Natural language search” systems are susceptible to bias and</p>	<p>NetU handles the way data from external, third-party sources are ingested and transferred to the METICOS</p>	<p>PRE-DESIGN</p> <p>At this stage, we defined the external parties with which</p>	<p>DESIGN-DEVELOPMENT</p> <p>Bias mitigation measures are not part of NetU’s</p>	<p>DEPLOYMENT</p>

	<p>discriminatory input. These user interfaces should contain appropriate mechanisms to prevent such input (for example, by “black-listing” discriminatory search parameters). This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and included in their reports.</p>	<p>platform. This means that NetU had not developed any algorithm dealing with any kind of data and therefore bias mitigation measures cannot be applicable to this task.</p> <p>NetU could only make sure the synergies of the interface are compliant to the EC recommendations relative to bias.</p>	<p>the interface would have to deal. It was important to define the scope of the use of the external parties as well as the data need to be collected from these.</p> <p>One can see that bias mitigation measures had to be applied on the third-party providers’ side. Once again, the interface only transfers data from one point to another, thus bias cannot appear.</p> <p>Third-party sources include data that police (Cypriot, Hellenic, Estonian and Romanian) uploads through a user interface that concern the origin of the passengers and their usage of the automated border control machines.</p> <p>Other source of data is the AeroDataBox from which the METICOS platform intakes</p>	<p>responsibilities as this task only deals with transferring data from external sources to the METICOS platform. The way they are processed and therefore any bias that can emerge, was to be handled by partners dealing with algorithm creation and data handling.</p> <p>NetU had to ensure the safe, timely and in the correct format transfer of data coming from third-parties to the METICOS platform. No bias can emerge during this process.</p>	<p>The output of the METICOS platform is not handled by NetU at all.</p>
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			<p>flight delay information and finally questionnaires provided by the project to random passengers.</p> <p>Questionnaires introduced by the consortium are also another source of input data that go through the interface created by NetU.</p>		
T9.1 (SIMAVI)	<p>The integration, validation and verification plan should include elements to test for bias and discrimination. Where bias or discrimination is detected, mechanisms should be implemented to remove it. This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and</p>	<p>The technical partners have periodic technical meetings. The integration, validation and verification plan was discussed and is still evolving. It will be completed in the following weeks with relevant tests for bias and discrimination.</p>	N/A	N/A	N/A

	included in their reports.				
T9.3 (ICCS)	When providing access to the data analysis algorithms, the Interactive Visual Analytics module should provide appropriate mechanisms to allow for human-readable auditing of data processing in order to assess bias and corresponding bias remediation processes. This should be monitored by the Ethics Board and assessed in their reports.	The DTVA component aims to only visualize the analytics results and does not in any case enable access to the data or the data analysis algorithms.	NA	NA	NA
T10.3	T9.3 (Pilot #2: Travellers	T9.3 will include in the questionnaire the	Physical limitations have been neglected at the first stage.	Gender and diversity aspects have been integrated in the	Concerning physical limitations, during a real-life

(JOAFG)	application trials and Pilot#2 Workshop): The two rounds of expert-based evaluations conducted by JOAFG should include assessment of bias and discrimination. The personal evaluation questionnaires should include questions regarding bias and discrimination.	recommendation to ask for experiences with discriminatory actions and bias.	Reason for this is that it would not provide added benefits to the results of the questionnaire. The direct experience of physical limitations in interaction with the system would provide a better result than the abstract interpretation of an unknown technical feature.	questionnaire. This includes gender and age. Concerning physical limitations, JOAFG takes the role of a representative for vulnerable groups from their experience with patient transport, care and Ambient Assisted Living (Technology usage).	pilot at Athens and Larnaca, wheelchairs will be used to provide qualitative insights into the possible issues by using an ABC from perspective of usability and user acceptance of currently available systems as a indicator for future developments.
T10.4 (JOAFG)	Documentation regarding the system's features, as well as the exhibition of its operation and capabilities, should include	T10.4 will follow the suggestion to integrate awareness about discrimination potentials and bias in the training concept for the METICOS system usage.	For the pre design phase, the algorithms have been not clear enough to provide a deeper understanding of the discriminatory power of the AI algorithms. Therefore, the training was focused on getting to know the	During the design and development stage of the project, the AI algorithms have been further developed according to the available data sources. Still, for the first training, there was not sufficient data about the AI	For the deployment stage, the training will include an own section about AI and how to work with AI systems in daily context. An understanding about the data sources and basic statistical analysis will be provided to practitioners

	<p>detailed information regarding the potential for bias or discrimination in the system’s output or usage. Because people have a tendency to trust AI systems more than they deserve (see: Schmidt et al. "Transparency and trust in artificial intelligence systems." Journal of Decision Systems 29.4 (2020): 260-278; High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence. 'Ethics Guidelines For Trustworthy AI'. Brussels: European Commission,</p>		<p>descriptive statistical data set at the dashboard without interpretation by the AI system.</p>	<p>algorithms to take them further into account for the training.</p>	<p>to allow a feasibility check of the provided data of the system. This competences will be also used to further develop the AI algorithms in feedback loops to increase the match between experience and data driven models.</p> <p>The JOAFG team suggests to the developers a Reporting function in the dashboard to allow a instant feedback for the AI if something is not according to the experience of the expert and provides a misunderstanding in the analysis result and could lead to unsupervised discrimination</p>
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	2019), the limits and weaknesses of the project's systems should be included in end-user training.				
T11.1 (ViLABS)	Webinars & tutorials, especially end-users hackathons, should indicate the system's weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities. It is important that the market is informed about the limitations and weaknesses of	Following the description of Task 11.1 and the DoA Webinars & tutorials, end-users hackathons, are being foreseen during M26 – M30 and for sure after the initial application of the Trials. Project webinars, training as well as dissemination activities, in general, will take into account the information provided by the relevant project partners and will disseminate the project outputs accordingly. Potential system's weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, will be	Presentation bias (Biases arising from how information is presented on the Web, via a user interface, due to rating or ranking output, or through users' own self-selected biased interactions). - METICOS will prepare a detailed introduction to – information on the system's weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities. User interaction bias (Arises when a user imposes their	Presentation bias (Biases arising from how information is presented on the Web, via a user interface, due to rating or ranking output, or through users' own self-selected biased interactions). - METICOS will prepare a detailed introduction to – information on the system's weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities. User interaction bias (Arises when a user imposes their	Presentation bias (Biases arising from how information is presented on the Web, via a user interface, due to rating or ranking output, or through users' own self-selected biased interactions). - METICOS will prepare a detailed introduction to – information on the system's weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities.

	<p>METICOS, as well as its benefits.</p>	<p>included in the relevant activities providing this way with a crystal-clear understanding to all relevant stakeholders engaged by the project activities. As WP11 is the Dissemination and Exploitation WP or as it is stated in the DoA the “Raising awareness and exploitation roadmap” WP, there is no research making or technology development in it. WP11 and especially task 11.1 work around the communication and dissemination of the knowledge, information, processes and activities and results organized and implemented by the rest of METICOS tasks.</p>	<p>own self-selected biases and behavior during interaction with data, output, results, etc.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - METICOS will prepare a detailed introduction – information on the system’s weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities in order to decrease the potential user interaction bias <p>Evaluation bias (Arises when the testing or external benchmark populations do not equally represent the various parts of the user population or from the use of performance metrics that are</p>	<p>own self-selected biases and behavior during interaction with data, output, results, etc.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - METICOS will prepare a detailed introduction – information on the system’s weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities in order to decrease the potential user interaction bias <p>Evaluation bias (Arises when the testing or external benchmark populations do not equally represent the various parts of the user population or from the use of performance metrics that are</p>	<p>User interaction bias (Arises when a user imposes their own self-selected biases and behavior during interaction with data, output, results, etc.).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - METICOS will prepare a detailed introduction – information on the system’s weaknesses, including potential for error, bias, and discrimination, both within the systems and through end-user activities in order to decrease the potential user interaction bias <p>Evaluation bias (Arises when the testing or external benchmark populations do not equally represent the various parts of the user population or from the use of</p>
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			<p>not appropriate for the way in which the model will be used).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least for the METICOS webinars, tutorials and such, (as it is not applicable for the rest of Task11.1 activities) METICOS will take into account the intersectional approach and try to include in the activities (if the activity is being organized by METICOS) the best possible representation of the relevant user population. <p>Exclusion bias (When specific groups or user populations are excluded from testing and subsequent analyses).</p>	<p>not appropriate for the way in which the model will be used).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least for the METICOS webinars, tutorials and such, (as it is not applicable for the rest of Task11.1 activities) METICOS will take into account the intersectional approach and try to include in the activities (if the activity is being organized by METICOS) the best possible representation of the relevant user population. <p>Exclusion bias (When specific groups or user populations are excluded from testing and subsequent analyses).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least for the METICOS webinars, 	<p>performance metrics that are not appropriate for the way in which the model will be used).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least for the METICOS webinars, tutorials and such, (as it is not applicable for the rest of Task11.1 activities) METICOS will take into account the intersectional approach and try to include in the activities (if the activity is being organized by METICOS) the best possible representation of the relevant user population. <p>Exclusion bias (When specific groups or user populations are excluded from testing and subsequent analyses).</p>
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			<p>- At least for the METICOS webinars, tutorials and such, (as it is not applicable for the rest of Task 11.1 activities) METICOS will take into account the intersectional approach and try to include in the activities (if the activity is being organized by METICOS) the best possible representation of the relevant user population.</p> <p>Relevant information will be available in D11.3 Dissemination, Communication and exploitation final progress report to be delivered on project month 36.</p>	<p>tutorials and such, (as it is not applicable for the rest of Task 11.1 activities) METICOS will take into account the intersectional approach and try to include in the activities (if the activity is being organized by METICOS) the best possible representation of the relevant user population.</p> <p>Relevant information will be available in D11.3 Dissemination, Communication and exploitation final progress report to be delivered on project month 36.</p>	<p>- At least for the METICOS webinars, tutorials and such, (as it is not applicable for the rest of Task 11.1 activities) METICOS will take into account the intersectional approach and try to include in the activities (if the activity is being organized by METICOS) the best possible representation of the relevant user population.</p> <p>Relevant information will be available in D11.3 Dissemination, Communication and exploitation final progress report to be delivered on project month 36.</p>
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5 Mitigation measures

For each impact on human rights having been evaluated in the previous section, the table below summarizes the mitigation measures having been identified.

Table 15 - Summary of the identified mitigation measures

Origin of the impact	Explanation	Recommendations/mitigation measures
Potential undercoverage bias due to target groups not adequately represented in the METICOS pilots' and research' samples.	The research results of the METICOS project might be biased in case of insufficient representation of the different impacted groups of persons identified in section 3.	<p>During the pilots, it is recommended to Involve all target groups identified in section 3.1 of this Deliverable.</p> <p>If it is not possible to engage with all of these target groups during the pilots, a valid alternative would be to engage with their representatives or with civil society organizations that can give voice to their concerns (for example, during workshops with partners and stakeholders – see section 6). This is also relevant for children since it was decided not to involve them during the pilots, as their consent to participate would not be considered as freely given (only adults over 18 with a capacity to consent will be able to participate).</p>
The collection and processing by border control technologies of biometric data (facial image, fingerprints) to verify the identity of the document's holder.	The collection and processing of biometric data (facial image, fingerprints) to verify the identity of the document's holder might (or not) appear to be a disproportionate interference with the rights to privacy and data protection, right to non-discrimination, etc.	In the questionnaires (as well as in the METICOS tablet & mobile applications), it is recommended to include questions reflecting the human rights' concerns deriving from the storage of biometrics in travel documents. A draft list of questions has been established in order to be discussed in workshops to be organized with partners and external stakeholders (see section 6).

<p>The use by border control technologies of EU large-scale IT systems (SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc.) to databases to determine eligibility of border crossing according to the pre-defined rules.</p>	<p>The use of EU processing of personal data (including biometrics) in centralized IT systems for border control management might appear (or not) to create a disproportionate interference with the rights to privacy and data protection, right to non-discrimination, etc.</p>	<p>In the questionnaires (as well as in the METICOS tablet & mobile applications), it is recommended to include questions reflecting the human rights' concerns deriving from the processing of personal data (including biometrics) in EU large-scale IT systems. A draft list of questions has been established.</p>
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the travellers' data within the METICOS platform such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deanonimization of the primary and secondary data being processed by the METICOS platform. • Illegitimate access to primary and secondary data processed by the METICOS platform. 	<p>In case of data breaches in the METICOS platform, border guards' staff might take unfair individual decisions towards travellers. Such decisions might impact different human rights, depending on the concrete circumstances.</p>	<p>A DPIA has been conducted in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”. A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR.</p>
<p>Confidentiality breaches of the border guard staff's data within the METICOS platform.</p>	<p>In case of breaches of border guard's data in the METICOS platform, the staff may be discriminated by their employers.</p>	<p>A DPIA has been conducted in D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)”. A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the</p>

		measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR.
Potential use of Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) during pilots in order to detect the travellers' acceptance.	Using Facial Emotion Recognition cameras during the pilots might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.	At this stage of the project, it was decided not to use cameras with facial emotion recognition as a data source of the METICOS platform.
The potential collection of data from the travellers' documents by non-authorized border staff.	The collection of data directly from travel documents by non-authorized border staff might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers.	It was decided not to collect data directly from travel documents. It was considered that it is not necessary for the purposes of the METICOS project to collect information enabling the individualization of each traveler/border control staff member (first name, last name, date of birth, travel document number, etc.).
The potential connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, ETIAS, etc.	The connection of the METICOS platform to border control databases such as SIS, VIS, EES, etc might create a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such interferences might have impacts on other fundamental rights depending on the concrete circumstances.	It was decided not to collect personal data from Border Control Databases such as VIS, SIS, EES, ETIAS, etc. It was considered that such extremely sensitive data were absolutely not needed for the purposes of the project.
The data collection from Twitter and other social media.	Retrieving any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and mining the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies might create	A DPIA has been conducted in D3.1 – "Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)". A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the

	a disproportionate interference in the rights to privacy and data protection of travellers. Such a data processing could also potentially lead to an interference with the freedom of expression.	processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. DPIAs are important tools for accountability, as they help controllers not only to comply with requirements of the GDPR, but also to demonstrate that appropriate measures have been taken to ensure compliance with the GDPR.
Lack of identification and mitigation of biases that might occur in the development lifecycle of components/technologies of METICOS which are based on Artificial Intelligence.	<p>Technology based on AI has broader impacts on fundamental rights than traditional software.</p> <p>Data sets, models and algorithms used by AI systems may suffer from the inclusion of bias. The continuation of such biases could lead to unintended (in)direct prejudice and discrimination against certain groups or people, potentially exacerbating prejudice and marginalisation.</p>	In order to identify the potential biases that may arise in any phase of the development of the METICOS components, we used the NIST Special Publication 1270 – “Towards a Standard for Identifying and Managing Bias in Artificial Intelligence” ⁸⁷ . As for the mitigation measures that might be used to manage the identified biases, the requirements listed in the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI were taken into account.

⁸⁷ This publication is available free of charge from <https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.1270>.

6 Audit and review of the HRIA

The review and audit stage of a Human Right impact assessment aims at ensuring independent evaluation and, if necessary, of independent intervention of the HRIA process. It especially focuses on the finalisation of the HRIA, by reviewing and assessing whether the process has been successfully conducted and whether the assessor has ensured follow-ups of the relevant findings. However, the review and audit stage also plays a role during the entire HRIA process, for it can steer the process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.

The figure below illustrates the envisaged timeline to proceed to both the review and audit processes of the HRIA.

Figure 4 - HRIA's timeline

The following sub-sections describe the envisaged review and audit processes of the HRIA.

6.1 Review process of the HRIA

The aim of the review stage of the HRIA is to evaluate the findings of this HRIA (as well as the findings of D3.1 – “Impact assessment and recommendations (first version)” so as to provide constructive feedback for improving the execution of the HRIA process.

In particular, during the review process, the following issues need to be addressed:

- Are all human rights impacts identified?
- In determining mitigation measures, are all efforts made to first avoid the impact altogether, and if this is not possible to reduce, mitigate and remediate the impacts?

In order to be able to conduct their mission, the reviewers must have sufficient ethical or legal knowledge as well as expertise in the specific research field of project. In addition, the views of independent experts need to be provided. Therefore, the reviewers of this HRIA will be both the project partners as well as external stakeholders such as lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, etc. It is also important to collect the views of the

different groups of persons being impacted by the border control technologies being identified in section 3.1.

In February 2023, two workshops were organized with external stakeholders:

- the first workshop involved stakeholders from the sector of law and AI to discuss the implications of Artificial Intelligence on fundamental rights.
- the second workshop involved stakeholders representing travellers' categories in order to discuss issues of representativeness during the project's data collections.

The minutes of these meetings are included in Annexes 1 and 2 of this Deliverable.

6.2 Audit process of the HRIA

In addition to the review process described in the previous sub-section, an audit process conducted by the Ethical Board is foreseen with the aim to steer the HRIA process in the right direction and help correcting mistakes if they occur.

As a reminder, the Ethical Board has been established by D1.8 – “GEN - Requirement No. 11”. The role of the Ethical Board is to monitor the activities and outputs of the project independently, ethically and legally.

As illustrated in figure 3 :

- the first version of this HRIA has been submitted for audit to the Ethical Board in July and August 2022. The recommendations of the Ethical Board are included in D1.10 – “GEN – Requirement No. 13”.
- the final version of this HRIA was submitted to the Ethical Board in order to be audited. Therefore, two meetings with the Ethical Board were organized on March 21st and 22nd 2023. Its recommendations were taken into before submission of Deliverable to the European Commission. The minutes of these two meetings will be integrated in D1.10 – “GEN – Requirement No. 13”.

7 Conclusion

This Deliverable (D3.7) consists into a “final version of the report on human rights impact assessment”. A first version of the Human rights impact assessment was submitted on M12.

After having detailed the scope(s) of the HRIA, the target groups and the human rights being impacted, this first version identifies relevant mitigation measures and recommendations in order to avoid the negative impacts altogether, and if this is not possible, to reduce, mitigate and remediate these impacts. It should be noted, however, that the scope of this HRIA does not cover specific implementations of the METICOS platform in the post project phase. It is indeed the ethical responsibility of end-users wishing to use the METICOS platform to update and adapt this HRIA by taking into account the particular elements of their specific implementation (political context, target groups that should be considered, etc.).

In comparison with the first version, this final version addresses issues related to identification and mitigation of biases. It also takes into account the outcomes of two workshops organized in February 2023: the first workshop involved stakeholders from the sector of law and AI to discuss the implications of Artificial Intelligence on fundamental rights; the second one involved stakeholders representing travellers' categories in order to discuss issues of representativeness during the project's data collections. Finally, it should be noted that this Deliverable was reviewed by the project's Ethical Advisory Board before submission to the EC.

Annex 1: Minutes of the workshop on the implications of Artificial Intelligence

Title: Workshop on Human Rights impact assessment - Meeting with key stakeholders from the sector of Law and AI

Date: 13th of February 2023 – 10:00-12:00 CET on Teams

Experts:

- **Ms Anastasia Karagianni:** is a PhD student in the Faculty of Law at the University of Athens. Her Ph.D research is focused on the implementation of gender equality and non-discrimination principles in the international and European regulatory frameworks about Artificial Intelligence.
- **Ms Alessandra Calvi:** is researcher at the VUB/LSTS. Her research interests include the interrelationships between law and technology, in particular between data protection and the circular economy.
- **Mr Nikos Ioannidis:** works as a PhD researcher at the Law, Science, Technology and Society (LSTS) Research Group at the Faculty of Law and Criminology in the Vrije Universiteit Brussel (VUB). He is appointed to the Brussels Laboratory for Data Protection & Privacy Impact Assessments (d.pia.lab), where he is conducting his PhD research.

Agenda

Time	Topic of discussion	Speakers
10:00-10:10	Welcome & Introduction	Ms Danai Kyrkou (VIL)
10:10-10:20	The METICOS tools: The social sensing toolkit and the Big Data Analytics framework	METICOS partners (ICCS and NTNU)
10:20-10:30	Presentation of the HRIA of METICOS	Mr Franck Dumortier (VUB)
10:30-10:45	Expert presentation I	Ms Anastasia Karagianni (NKUA)
10:45-11:00	Expert presentation II	Ms Alessandra Calvi (VUB)
11:00-11:15	Expert presentation III	Mr Nikolaos Ioannidis (VUB)
11:15-11:45	Round table & questions	
<i>Closing</i>		

Minutes

After having presented the work carried out in WP6, one of the experts asked why the processing of the location of the authors' tweets is needed to measure technology acceptance and how this could lead to bias.

It was answered that in the sentiment analysis carried out in WP6, location was considered because the perception extraction is not only based on age groups or gender, but also on what is the location or nationality of the user of the social media. The profile country of the user who posted the tweet is being processed (to which country or to which region that user belong). When we start aggregating the results and we see that for some of the location countries, we are getting many travelers and for other many less, this might raise some bias. Therefore, the model which predicts the technology acceptance score is either not suppressing or not actually ignoring those data points where for a specific country there are a smaller amount of points. Of course, while collecting the data, it's obvious that more tweets are posted from certain countries than others. Hence, the profiles from some countries have dominance in the model. In order to have the technology acceptance score not generalized to all the travelers, it should be trained in a way such that it should consider the different location impacts. Based on the data collection, the model may be more knowledgeable about some countries versus others.

A second expert asked about the data collection being carried out in WP6. More insight was asked about why it had been considered to use the Twitter academic API to get the full archive of tweets.

It was answered that, if we would have gone for the Twitter Free API, we only would get back to seven days of recent data. A second option was the Twitter premium API, which gives access to data back to a few years but this feature must be paid. The Twitter academic API provides access to the full archive of data and is mainly designed for research purposes, so we could use it in the research project. We needed to first draft the request for that API and, once that request was approved, we could start accessing it.

The same expert asked whether this Twitter academic API disaggregates information on the basis of for example, gender, race, ethnicity of the people that are tweeting. It was answered that this was not the case. The expert replied that this could be quite a problem, to a certain extent, because it doesn't allow to evaluate how different people perceive the border control technologies. Twitter itself and social media in general provides a huge amount of data and it's useful for training the models. However, if it is not possible to disaggregate information based on gender, race and so on, there are really risks of invisibility. The concerns of people that may really have an issue with border control technology may not be highlighted. Another thing that the same expert asked is how it is possible to infer a sort of sentiment from a tweet. It was answered that the model that we are using is the most recent one from the literature, a state-of-the-art model, that does not only work on the basis of keywords or words that are involved in the tweet: the model also infers its meaning based on the context in the neighboring words as well as on the context of the whole tweet. So the model that we are using is quite good to extract the sentiment or emotion in a very good way not only from simple, but also from indirect or complex text as well.

Regarding the first question of the expert concerning the issue of under representation, it was added that the WP6 component is only one of the components of the METICOS platform, amongst many others. The METICOS consortium is aware of the questions of underrepresentation during the pilots, but also in some components. One of the mitigation measures is that we engage with different, let's say, minorities in workshops to get their input and to give voice to their concerns. In case we cannot engage with these “minorities” during the pilots, we try to engage with their representatives during workshops. But in the WP6 component itself, there is a kind of bias that we still should consider.

It was also detailed that the WP6 model is based on gender (male/female), age groups and location. At the end, on the dashboard that is made available to end-users, the technology acceptance score is divided into these different groups as well as on the country and location.

The work carried out in WP7 was then presented to the experts. The aim of WP7 is to harmonize and fuse data that comes from various sources and for this purpose we have developed a data model. Moreover, WP7 provides a portfolio, a framework of machine learning and statistical algorithms, in addition to data analytics techniques. The final purpose is to expose the results of this analysis to our stakeholders using an interactive dashboard. Focusing on what kind of output we produce, we are able to handle text in various language but we wanted to be able to provide a language agnostic model. Therefore, we translated all languages being used to English (we preprocess the text). In the end, the output that we're able to produce is some sentiments. For the sentiment extraction, we use pre trained model;, we're not building our own from scratch. So we're using state-of-the-art machine learning models that are trained and evaluated.

Moreover, it's very important to mention that, with the view to handle some of the bias introduced to display the statistics in a cross tabular way, such as what is the acceptance based on age and gender or what would be the operational data based on age and gender, we're not just using a raw score, but we're able to go into more detail about these parameters and these attributes and to measure what's the weight of each influencing factor that may or may not finally influence acceptance.

Furthermore, a bias identification pipeline is being introduced in the METICOS platform. This pipeline was not built from scratch (we base ourselves on a lot of work that has already been done on fair machine learning). In particular, we use the AI fairness 360 Python package that includes a comprehensive set of metrics and models to test for biases and mitigate these biases in datasets and models. Various types of biases can be introduced in various stages of the processing. What we aim to do is basically to be able to identify bias in the raw data and also after the pre-processing stage. These are basically the two stages that we are focusing on. We're not focusing on the processing or post processing techniques. For these stages, the algorithms being used should embed the fairness notion in them. Focusing on handling raw data, the sample dataset that we have is balanced. Concerning the preprocessing stage, we used techniques such as reweighing to be to arrive at a fairer machine learning model. In addition, we have been using and testing this bias identification pipeline. With an initial set of questionnaire data, we have not found any bias introduced, at least for the attribute of gender.

An expert wondered why we focused to address the bias at the preprocessing stages. According to this expert, it's already a good strategy to try to address bias in the preprocessing stages, but she believes that in the long term, it would be interesting to perhaps trying to check if actually the predictions are actually correct.

It was answered to the expert that the idea would be to identify bias at each stage and monitor each stage in order to ensure that the data being produced are unbiased and handled correctly. However, she explained that we have paid more attention to the initial stages because then we will also be able to provide more balanced datasets to the other technical partners as well, which may also use these datasets. It would be possible for us to include at least one algorithm that handles more the in processing and the post processing stages. The expert's comment will be taken into account to see whether we could include something more. But at the same time, it was recalled that the bias identification metrics already used are able to see whether an algorithm has produced an unfair result based on, let's say, age, gender, etc. So we're already able to identify bias in any stage, but the way to handle this bias was only focused on the first two stages.

The same expert asked a second question related to the fact that gender was considered in a kind of binary terminology (male/female), but her impression is that for this kind of border automated border control technologies, representation of non-binary people is important because they really fear the accuracy of the technology towards them. Therefore, the expert asked how we plan to reflect the fact that gender is not really a binary construct.

It was answered to the expert that we're able to reflect that gender is not really a binary construct in the gender attribute, but the way that it's populated will depend on the data that we have. So, if we have non-binary people in the data collected, this will be reflected in the gender attribute. As a reminder, it's very important to note that the machine learning learns on the data that it has already access to. So, it will depend also on the ground truth data that we have and to which we're exposed to. We need to take care of having access to data concerning underrepresented people, minorities to be able to produce more robust results. It was added that the METICOS consortium is aware of the potential underrepresentation of some target groups ("minorities") such as transgender, sex workers, people with different colors, people with disabilities, elderly, children, undocumented migrants, etc. So we try to involve representatives of these target groups in workshops because we know that we cannot have a sufficient representation of these target groups during the pilots or during data collection.

Another expert was concerned about how the sentiments will be evaluated from users because only Twitter was chosen and no other social media. According to this expert, Twitter is mostly used for political topics and is maybe not relevant enough to obtain acceptance scores about border control technologies. Furthermore, according to that expert, tweets reflect extreme opinions. Accordingly, the acceptance model could reflect the views of the ultra-right wing. Regarding the methods and tools, the same expert asked to clarify what is the second line check that was mentioned (the human in the loop concept). She also asked: "Who is the human?" and "What is the loop?". In addition, the same expert shared some thoughts about replication of bias in datasets. She mentioned a real case scenario in the United States in which a transgender person who was in a gender reassignment process tried to cross the borders. According to this person's official documents, this person was a female and, given the gender reassignment process, this person could not be identified by the system, because of the binary distinction of gender in their data set. The same expert recalled that border control technologies are mostly based on biometric data. The processing of biometric data raises questions related to identification of non-binary transgender people and replication of race bias. Regarding the question of how comfortable travelers feel when using border control technologies, the same expert

shared doubts about whether “minorities” could share their honest replies because some travelers might be human trafficking victims or gender-based violence survivors that are fleeing from their country with their child because they don't have any other alternatives. Possibly, such categories of travelers might have many sentiments they want to cover when facing border management controls. The same reasoning applies to humiliation concerns of such categories of travelers. According to the expert, “minorities” may not realize the impact of the use of biometric data. In general, travelers are not even aware of how biometric data is being used. Hence, in the METICOS platform, the explainability principle should be integrated into the METICOS platform. Issues of discrimination should also be examined.

The expert concluded by reminding us that, in general, the AI systems are designed and are programmed based on the binary distinction of gender. Hence, probably transgender people, sex workers or people in gender reassignment processes will be really impacted and probably there are also correlations with other factors such as class and race. In order to mitigate all these biases, the expert thinks that the composition of AI development teams should involve people from different demographic backgrounds and from different gender representations. According to the expert, as far as Greece is concerned, people who are working in positions of software engineering, programmers, data analytics, data analysis, and data science are mostly white, CIS, and straight. According to statistics, 75%, of teams are men, and there are few women and non-binary transgender people who are working in these positions. We need a more intersectional approach to mitigate this kind of bias.

In addition, border control managers should be aware that not only the factors of gender and age might generate bias but also race. Moreover, they probably have unconscious bias. Indeed, biases are replicated in the systems by the humans because we have unconscious or conscious biases. Therefore, training of the personnel is really needed for the mitigation of biases. As far as the explainability issue is concerned, the expert believes that the users of the AI systems should know about the process that is going on and about the outcome of this process. They need to have explanations regarding the data that is used and the way that this data was used. They need to have explanations regarding fairness and of course responsibility. This means that they should know who will be accountable in case of a design flaw of the system.

After the expert's presentation, it was answered that the METICOS consortium works with data that we are able to collect. If we cannot get data about for example, transgender persons, sex workers, people who hide their emotions, we cannot really use it. However, if a technology acceptance score comes low continuously, then we may see that the technology acceptance dropped for a while and ask ourselves the reason for such an output (Why is that?). Our systems could give indications of something happening. Hence, it's not that we don't want to cover transgender persons or minority groups, it's just that we don't have data about such minority groups. The way the system works is as follows: we collect data and then a profile is extracted: gender, age, nationality, education level, occupation, familiarity with technology and so on. As regards gender: if we collect data about males and females, then such profiles are extracted. But if we are able to get data about transgender persons, then we can make it part of this gender attribute. Same for age, for nationality and perceptions, subjectivity, sentiment, emotion and feedback on aspects of technology. Our interest in this project is to understand how each technology is perceived by the different groups. Any extreme acceptance

scores in positive or negative directions could point to the issues the expert was mentioning and we can analyze these variations in order to identify their cause.

Another expert focused on participation within the decision-making process of the general public. She asked to which extent we could try to incorporate this element that could empower people in the human right impact assessment. She understood that we wanted to involve several categories of people in the pilots and believed this is very good but she didn't understand whether the objective was to involve their participation in the human rights impact assessment. One of the main criticisms of impact assessment in general, not just human right impact assessments, it's that they are very much top down and not really empowering. They normally are the responsibility of entities that are decision makers, so by definition already at the top of the power chain. Hence, involving people whose voices normally are not listened to is very important.

It was answered to the expert that the role of the pilots is data collection for the measurement of acceptance. It's not a participatory activity to the human rights impact assessment because otherwise the questionnaires would be too long. However, in the questionnaires, there are some questions that are in between acceptance and the impacts on human rights because, of course, the travelers' acceptance is also related their expectations on the impacts on their human rights. In addition, we are aware that we are not easily collecting data to be to have represent sufficient representativeness of minority groups such as transgender persons, sex workers, undocumented travellers, etc. And that's why we plan to engage with them with them during workshops to get their concerns. Of course, such concerns need to be reflected afterwards in the algorithms, but we need to get some data collection from somewhere.

A second concern of this expert was related to our definitions of the people impacted by border control technologies. She realized that we had focused on impacts for travelers but were also mentioning that border guards themselves could be impacted by the border control technologies. For example, they may fear that more automated control will take away their jobs. However, the concerns of border staff members were considered as legitimate interests instead of fundamental rights. The expert asked clarifications about this since that the right to worker is somehow mentioned in Article 15 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights.

It was answered to the expert that we are not excluding the border guards' staff from the human rights impact assessment even if the most sensitive group is of course the travelers. Indeed, there are some impacts on workers. These impacts could enter into the scope of Article 15 of the Charter and this will be analyzed more in depth once the pilot with border guards has been conducted.

The last expert wondered how Twitter had been chosen for this research.

It was answered to the expert that the first reason for choosing Twitter is that Twitter was the only social media platform having the data we needed to assess the acceptance of border control technologies (people's tweets on their experiences or their thoughts). LinkedIn was not suitable because it did not contain the appropriate data. The second reason for choosing Twitter is related to the API to collect the data: Twitter is the easiest API to use and to collect the data. It was also referred to the Deliverable 6.2 that explains in very detail how we did the survey of social media sources, the available social media sources and, based on different requirement and criteria, how we selected

Twitter. It was also added that Twitter was not the only data source: travellers' questionnaires are also being used.

Annex 2: Minutes of the workshop on travellers' categories and biases

Title: Workshop on travellers' categories and biases

Date: 13th of February 2023 – 14:00-16:00 CET on Teams

Experts:

- **Prof Anna Krasteva:** is the president of the Policy and Citizens' Observatory. She is professor of Political Science, Doctor Honoris Causa of the University of Lille, France, editor-in-chief of 'Southeastern Europe' (brill.com/seeu), director of CERMES (Centre for European Refugees and Migration Studies), Dept. of Political Sciences, NBU. She is president and member of numerous international scientific boards. Her main fields of research and teaching are migration, refugee and border policies and politics, national populism, radicalization and far-right youth, post-democracy, crises and leadership, civic activism and citizenship.
- **Prof Eleonore Kofman:** is Professor of Gender, Migration and Citizenship at the Middlesex University of London. She is the co-Director of the Migration and Displacement stream of the UKRI GCRF Hub – Gender, Justice and Security (2019-2024), led by the LSE Centre for Women, Peace and Security and co-Investigator of the project Gendered Dynamics of Labour Migrations. Middlesex collaborates with academic and NGO partners across the Middle East and South Asia.
- **Mr Francesco Murendu:** is a leading analyst on innovation and technology policies with a special focus on digital transformation, big data, artificial intelligence, eGovernment, smart cities, social innovation, future science and citizen science.
- **Sabrina Sanchez:** Sabrina Sanchez is the Coordinator of ESWA European Sex Workers' Rights Alliance. Born in Mexico in 1981, graduated in Communication at UNAM (Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México).

Agenda

Time	Topic of discussion	Speakers
14:00-14:10	Welcome & Introduction	Ms Danai Kyrkou (VIL)
14:10-14:20	Presentation of the METICOS questionnaires used during the project pilot activities	METICOS partners (AIT & Joafg)
14:20-14:30	Presentation of the HRIA of METICOS	Dr Franck Dumortier (VUB)
14:30-14:40	Expert presentation I	Prof Anna Krasteva (Policy and Citizens' Observatory)
14:40-14:50	Expert presentation II	Prof Eleonore Kofman (MXD)
14:50-15:00	Expert presentation III	Mr Francesco Murendu (Lisbon Council)

15:00-15:10	Expert presentation IV	Ms Sabrina Sanchez (ESWA)
15:20-15:50	Round table & questions	
<i>Closing</i>		

In order to introduce the workshop, JOAFG presented the processes being followed to collect data from the travelers via questionnaires during the pilots.

During the pilots, where we are mainly using questions for collecting the data from travelers concerning the technology acceptance of automated border control points. We support our pilot actions with an online questionnaire. At the airport in Athens, we will provide roll-ups standing at the automated border control points and we want to allow a constant feedback of passengers through a QR code. We decentralized data collections so we can have these roll-ups everywhere around the airports at the same time and we can leave them there for as long as we want to. This system allows the direct access towards the online questionnaire. Just after having passed the ABC gate, travellers have the chance to scan the QR code and come directly prompted to our website of the Lime Survey Questionnaire. We have chosen Lime survey because we can run the server on our own premises: a dedicated server running within the European Union located in Vienna where we have full access and full control. For the data analysis, we use predefined evaluation sheets. By this we can, on the fly, do the evaluation of the data in a standardized manner and directly integrate the data in our findings. In order to draft the questionnaire, we started with the Technology Acceptance Model 2. This technology acceptance model is based on certain dimensions that are influencing the technology, acceptance. On this basis, we made some adjustments so to reduce the questions and dimensions while keeping the same significance levels. For each dimension, we have always the question “do the people agree to a certain statement?”. JOAFG then presented each question of the questionnaire related to the technology acceptance of facial recognition.

At the end of the process, we can compare the answers that we got from the questionnaires. Therefore, we have final questions such as “which gender do you feel you belong to”, “what is your age” (where we're providing slots) and then finally “are you citizen or resident, yes or no?”. With the two questions about gender and age, we have the indication for the sociodemographic information that we need to measure the technology acceptance in comparison with the data that we had from the 8000 sample (big survey with 8000 answers carried out previously by JOAFG and AIT).

After JOAFG’s introduction, VUB presented the legal and ethical tasks in METICOS so that the invited experts could understand everything that has been done from an ethical and legal perspective and also to better understand the scope of what was expected from them during the meeting.

In particular, VUB explained how the different impacted groups of travelers envisaged to be monitored by the METCOS platform were identified in the Human Right Impact Assessment. We based ourselves on the definitions of travelers in the Schengen Border Code. So basically, there is a distinction that's been made between persons enjoying the right to free movement under Union law and 3rd country nationals. But of course, in each of these groups, there are subgroups with different impacts on human rights: for example, holders of a visa may have other impacts than refugees, immigrants, asylum seekers, or undocumented travelers in general. In addition to this classification, other factors were taken into account that could modify the impact on human rights of the METICOS platform, such as language, gender, nationality, race, ethnicity, disabilities, etc. Of course, during the pilots, it's not easy to engage with all these kinds of participants. Therefore, we are aware that there might be an underrepresentation bias because we are not sure that we are targeting all the categories of people

that are not the “usual suspects” in our pilots. As an alternative, we try to engage with these underrepresented “minorities” by organizing workshops to make sure that we can give voice to their concerns. Indeed, the potential under coverage bias due to target groups not being adequately represented during the pilots makes it important to engage which stakeholders, civil society organizations, etc. that can give voice to the concerns of these target groups. Such groups are for example, children, people with disabilities, asylum seekers, refugees and undocumented travelers, people of different colors, sex workers, etc.

After VUB’s presentation, the first expert took the floor. She took a theoretical approach in her presentation because she did not want to go into the very technical details of the questionnaire nor of the METICOS platform. From a broader critical perspective (intellectual critique) inspired by the human rights perspective, she started with a small quotation from a demographer which said, 15 years ago, that in the near future, everybody will have a chip implemented in his body and so the mobility will be measured in real time. According to the first expert, today we do not have chips implemented, but we are producing all those data through our smartphones, Internet connections etc. Hence, Big data tracking impacts our mobility. Moreover, the digital border technologies are part of a much larger phenomenon that should not underestimate the political dimension: the technologies should not be presented in a kind of political vacuum. The use of technologies differ a lot, let's say, from one political context to another one. Therefore, to the question “Do you trust border control”, the same person could reply very differently at one border compared to another. In some political contexts, connections between databases can be considered as facilitating border control processes that simplify a little bit the traveler's life. But in general, it means that we enter into the conceptual universe of gigantic collections of sensitive data. Therefore, according to this expert, the questions in METICOS could have been asked in a more theoretical manner. For example, we could have asked questions such as “If a photo is taken every time you cross a border, how has it improved security ? How has it improved fight against terrorism ?”, etc. And not simply “how do you experience biometrics?” because it is very subjective. In the same idea, the expert shared that in 2022 they were 330,000 irregular border crossings in Europe with an increase of 64%. Hence, according to her, the more biometrical data are collected, the less security there is. Her conclusion was that our EU border policy is the maybe biggest threat to our values and the rule of law: what she calls “border policies border disorder”.

The second expert then took the floor. According to her, different borders have different meanings for people depending on who is controlling a border. Who is regulating a border has very different meanings and she thinks this needs to be considered. At the other hand, who is crossing the border is also important, as the acceptance of some categories of travelers will be very different. The capture of data runs across on all these categories and some of these might have much more fear of biometric data collections at borders. Another question that the expert asked herself is “why is the EU really so concerned that people accept the collection of data at borders?”. One might want to ask this kind of question because looking at travelers’ acceptance is an ethical concern in se. Certainly because it gives no overview of any of the exact problems that the different impacted groups might have when crossing the borders nor the difficulties that they could face. A discussion should also be held about proving oneself of being a valid person to be able to cross the border in the context of the EU desire to facilitate the crossing of borders and to create a seamless border control with data being collected almost without travelers being aware of it. According to the expert, this attempt is quite dangerous. It's almost taking away the idea of crossing borders with security. And that is precisely what borders are usually about: it's about trying to make you secure. For some of the categories of the impacted groups listed in the Human Rights Impact Assessment, this obscure collection of data is very problematic. One of the important issues is the misrecognition of stereotyped categories of travelers. Categories can be

stereotyped but this is an issue we ought to have in mind. There might be misrecognition of the age of the travelers in the documents, but it's also a question of determining what age somebody is. Another concern is the fact that people are likely to be stereotyped. Another example is religion: we know that when religions are being classified, the target is not religion in general but Islam in particular. We need to take that into consideration in relation to the kind of collection of data and what that means for those particular impacted groups. Lastly, the expert raised the issue of the ETIAS, which is going to be rolled out. According to her, again there is that question about how ETIAS will separate the desirable from the undesirable travelers. ETIAS might, for example, ask who your parents are and the answer to that question might impact whether we may be considered as an acceptable citizen. Another example is that we may be acceptable permanent residents but live in a street which the state regards as non-acceptable.

The third expert then took the floor. He believes that the Human Rights Impact Assessment that was carried out within the scope of the project is very interesting and believes that it is also quite complete in the sense that it evaluates both the border control modern technologies that are monitored by METICOS, but also the METICOS platform itself. It identifies exactly who are the basic stakeholders that will have their own data collected and that might have problems of privacy and of Human Rights. It also identifies the border control processes and the kinds of data being processed: data like biometric data, facial images, fingerprints or the processing of personal data in central IT systems. The expert recalled that, clearly, we are talking about very sensitive data because they are related to gender and skin color. We are talking about technologies that are very invasive, very intrusive and that can jeopardize the human rights because some ethnic groups and some nationalities can have difficulties to be recognized. Therefore, this expert suggested to monitor the questionnaires with the project's Advisory Board. It was answered to the expert that the questionnaires will be discussed during the next Ethical Advisory Board meeting.

The last expert then took the floor. She is representing sex workers and transexual persons that are not really aware when their data are getting collected. Because of the nature of their work and precisely because of the regulations and rules around sex work and prostitution, their concerns also intersect with the opacity of the data being collected. With the regulations around the freedom of movement (or the lack of freedom of movement), the need of proof when you cross a border is particularly important. As a transgender person, it's sometimes difficult to prove your identity when your document is old and doesn't reflect the changes that that you have gone through. Also, there is the question of what to do to your body, to yourself, in order to be more in line with the match of your image at borders. And of course, sometimes the documents don't match the data in the databases. There have been cases of transgender people that have been taken their nationality away because they were considered as providing false information and doing fraud. These are the big issues with these biometric measures at borders. In this in this sense, when you're a sex worker you have to prove that you are not a sex worker. This situation may lead sex workers to adopt strategies to avoid data collections. Therefore, according to this expert, as a community, sex workers need to make themselves aware of these collections of data and the different applicable regulations.

After the presentations of the four experts, the consortium members added a few comments.

There we are lots of issues raised by the experts related to the political context(s) and on the fact that the measurement of the acceptance of technology depends on the specific political context. It was recalled that, in METICOS, we're running pilots in different countries. We have different pilot sites and

we differentiate the answers depending on these sites. That's how we take into account the political context(s) in our results.

A second issue that was often recalled by the experts was the one of the opacity of the data collections and transfers at borders, that is also related to the interoperability of the border control databases at the European level. No questions related to the acceptability of the interoperability of databases are included in the questionnaire, but the questionnaire needed to be practically understandable, and it was hard to provide participants with in-depth information on how interoperability of the EU border control databases exactly works. In order to be able to answer a question about the acceptability of interoperability, participants should know at least, beforehand, what kind of data is being processed and what kind of impact it has on their human rights. And that was not easy to do for practical reasons (length of the questionnaire).

For what concerns the balance between biometrics and security, it was recalled that the scope of the project is to measure the acceptance of the technologies placed in the official borders. Hence, we do not measure the acceptance of technologies (such as drones) that monitor “natural” borders which could be used by migrants. In other words, we are not measuring the acceptance of measures against illegal immigration that are put in place in non-official borders.

Regarding the comments on ETIAS, the system is not in place yet. So, at this stage, the questionnaires were not drafted in relation to that system. Since our METICOS platform is based on the collection of data, we will have to wait for the ETIAS implementation before being able to measure its acceptance.

